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Final Assessment of M-ERA.NET 3

Final Report May 2026

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FOREWARD AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

On behalf of the M-ERA.NET network, I am pleased to present the final report of the assessment of M-ERA.NET 3. This report consolidates the assessment outcomes and provides an integrated account of the network's implementation, achievements and lessons learned, also applying a forward-looking approach by looking to the future of the network. Although in principle the task was to cover the M-ERA.NET 3 period (2021-2026), much of the analysis goes further back to the previous M-ERA.NET phases (2016-2022 and 2012-2016) presenting interesting trends over time.

The report has been prepared to support transparency, accountability and learning. It brings together the evidence collected through the assessment process and translates it into clear findings and practical observations relevant to research and innovation funders, policy-makers and stakeholders engaged in advanced materials, their application and related enabling technologies. The intention is to offer a reliable basis for understanding what has been delivered, how the network has operated, and which aspects merit continued attention in future programme design and implementation.

I would like to thank all partners for their sustained engagement and constructive collaboration throughout the assessment and review process, as well as the experts and stakeholders who contributed information, feedback and validation. I also acknowledge the work of the assessment team and the ample attention paid by the M-ERA.NET 3 management team that supported the whole assessment process.

M-ERA.NET has been built on the shared commitment of its partners to strengthen transnational cooperation, reduce fragmentation and support high-quality research and innovation through coordinated funding. I trust that this report will be useful for ongoing strategic reflection within the network and for the wider community interested in effective, collaborative approaches in advanced materials research.

Sincerely,

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Purpose, scope and audience

This report details the Final Assessment of M-ERA.NET 3, a transnational research and innovation network supporting advanced materials. It provides an integrated view of performance and impacts with a focus on issues relevant to funding agencies, policy-makers and research and innovation stakeholders in universities, research organisations and businesses. The assessment has examined how the network performed in terms of **efficiency, effectiveness, impacts, network health and connectivity, European added value and additionality**. It has also applied a **forward-looking approach** in relation to the future of the network and concludes with recommendations for improvement.

Evaluation approach and evidence base

The assessment applied an **ex-post, summative evaluation** design utilising **mixed methods** to gather and analyse the required evidence. This involved desk research and extended KPI/statistical analysis using programme and external datasets, interviews with network members and European Commission officers, in-depth interviews with funded project coordinators, and an online survey capturing the insights of both successful and unsuccessful applicants. Although, in principle, the task was to cover the M-ERA.NET 3 period (2021-2026), much of the analysis also addressed the previous M-ERA.NET phases (M-ERA.NET 2: 2016-2021 and even M-ERA.NET 1: 2012-2016) presenting trends over time and insights into the evolution of the network. The assessment also included bibliometric and patent analysis based on available final project reports. A forward-looking dimension was applied that guided the organisation of a Strategy Workshop structured around the results and findings of the assessment. The outputs of this workshop were incorporated in the final report and informed the recommendations for the future of the network.

Programme rationale and intervention logic

M-ERA.NET 3 was designed to mobilise and coordinate national and regional funding for transnational research and innovation (R&I) projects in advanced materials, while also strengthening collaboration among funding organisations and helping align priorities across countries and regions. The intervention logic linked activities related to call design, proposal selection and project support with horizontal activities that consolidate participating programmes and connect the network with wider European research and innovation communities. Immediate outcomes related to enabling and improving structured transnational collaboration, knowledge transfer and coordination. Medium-term objectives included enhanced cooperation between research actors and the mobilisation of critical mass in funding and expertise, with longer-term aspirations framed around reduced fragmentation leading to strengthened European Research Area, as well as strengthened industrial capabilities and contributions to broader European strategic objectives.

Network performance, health and connectivity

M-ERA.NET 3 was widely perceived as a **credible, professionally managed and operationally robust network**

as consistently evidenced across the interviews and survey responses. Consortium members and external stakeholders described a mature governance model that can coordinate a large partnership – the largest of its kind - and deliver regular calls at scale, while maintaining collegiality and smooth operation. The network's breadth has been a defining feature: participation spans a wide range of 35 EU13, EU14 and non-EU countries (including 14 regions), with stability in participation over time, and a core group of 11 countries that have participated in all calls since 2012. This scale and continuity are seen as central to M-ERA.NET's ability to reduce fragmentation and widen participation in advanced materials R&I.

International connectivity was emphasised as a comparative advantage. Internationalisation was reported as the dominant motivation among survey respondents and interviewees, with M-ERA.NET 3 (and previous phases) seen as an enabling platform for cross-border collaboration that many actors would find difficult to establish through national programmes. This is particularly relevant for smaller funders and [widening countries](#) seeking to overcome peripherality and limited domestic scale, and for third-country participants for whom M-ERA.NET 3 can serve as a structured entry point into EU-relevant collaboration.

Financial scale, mobilisation and leverage

Analysis of the data compiled by M-ERA.NET 3's coordination and management team showed that financial commitments have grown across the three phases of the network, with commitments rising from €114 million in M-ERA.NET 1 to €134 million in M-ERA.NET 2 and €215 million in M-ERA.NET 3. The actual funding levels increased notably in the calls that received top up funding from the European Commission (EC) (2016, 2021) but remained substantial in subsequent years. These patterns are indicators of the **sustained commitment of network members** and strong mobilisation of the research and innovation community.

This assessment also highlighted the significant value-for-money achieved by M-ERA.NET 3 as demonstrated by the **leverage effect** observed in the EC co-funded calls (leverage is defined as partner commitments divided by the EU top-up). For call 2021 the leverage is 5.35 based on partners' contributions of €58.9 million and EU top-up funding of €11.0 million. This is significantly higher than that reported for other similar networks or partnerships in Horizon Europe (in the [BMR 2024](#)). Combined with the sustained growth in financial commitment, this provides a compelling quantitative signal that the network can **mobilise significant national and regional investment** in advanced materials when delivered through a trusted and well-coordinated network mechanism.

Efficiency: delivery, administrative burden and process quality

Consortium members report that the **administrative workload is broadly similar to other networks**, and that coordination costs are not perceived as higher than elsewhere, especially given the scale of M-ERA.NET and the complexity of working across national systems. The programme's **credibility and clarity of call processes** are viewed as a strong asset, while M-ERA.NET procedures have been replicated as good practices in other networks and initiatives.

At project level, the evidence points to a researcher-friendly implementation experience that balances **transparency with manageable administrative requirements**. However, there remain **friction points** that affect operational efficiency, including differences in national rules, timelines and contracting processes that can create uneven start conditions across project consortia. These issues are not framed as undermining programme credibility, but they are presented as practical constraints that can reduce speed and predictability, which is a sensitive matter particularly for SMEs and industry actors.

Effectiveness: achievement of objectives and portfolio-level results

Effectiveness is assessed in relation to the programme's objectives hierarchy, beginning with mobilisation and participation in calls and extending to project outcomes and broader impacts. There has been a steady increase in the number of submitted proposals and individual applicants, with expected peaks in calls that were topped up by the EC (232 applications in 2016 and 493 in 2021) and sustained engagement beyond those peaks. The number of funded projects also shows the highest numbers in the EC-cofunded calls (46 in 2016 and 69 in 2021), but it remained between 40-50 projects in 2022 and 2023, whereas the calls in 2024 and 2025 have settled around 30 projects. This is evidence of **continued attractiveness and relevance** to the materials community, while also contributing to oversubscription pressures that require careful call design and evaluation management, as well as actions at the national level to better match budgets to interest.

A key comparative advantage highlighted is that **M-ERA.NET fills a functional gap** between national programmes and large Framework Programme instruments by supporting smaller, more manageable consortia, that address risky, mid-TRL research. For [widening countries](#), and early career or less experienced researchers this **complementarity is particularly valuable**. Evidence shows that EU13 participation has been rising in both membership and financial commitment over the years, i.e. from around € 8 million in M-ERA.NET 2 to € 12-14 million per call in M-ERA.NET 3. The **network also fills a thematic gap** in advanced materials as evidenced by the increasingly high number of proposals received in each call and the numerous interviews conducted for the purpose of the assessment.

Comparing M-ERA.NET (all phases) to other networks ([ERA-MIN](#), [FLAGERA](#) and [QuantERA](#)), the network funded 481 projects over 14 years, which is around **5 times the number of projects funded by the other networks** over their existence. It is also **half the number of projects supported by all the relevant calls** in both H2020 and Horizon Europe.¹ These projects account for total cost of around € 520 million, which is again almost five times the respective total project costs of the second largest network in this regard.

Besides the **stability** of the network, launching annual calls since 2012, interviewees valued the **genuine collaboration, and interdisciplinarity**. This resonates with the responses to the online survey, where the most commonly achieved outcomes were reported to be access to new international research institutions or universities, access to new know-how, peer-reviewed joint publications, and the creation of new scientific

¹ 514 RIA / IA projects in NMBP calls in H2020, 370 RIA / IA projects in Cluster 4 and 79 projects in the battery-related calls in Cluster 5 under Horizon Europe (963 projects in total).

methods or data. This is directly linked to **effectiveness in producing knowledge outputs and building durable networks**. The co-authorship analysis of the joint publications illustrated the **global reach** of the consortia and indicated **potential for ongoing impact** and collaboration beyond the funding period.

Impacts and impact pathways: scientific output, innovation and collaboration

The **highest expected impacts** are concentrated in research-oriented and collaboration-driven areas, which aligns closely with M-ERA.NET's mission. Respondents to the online survey reported very strong expectations of engagement in new research fields, enhanced knowledge base and skills, durable international collaborations, new international collaboration opportunities, and increased publications. These collaboration patterns were described as reinforcing capability building, access to specialised expertise and infrastructures, and the formation of long-standing collaboration that extend beyond individual project cycles. Similarly, improvements in reputation and network visibility were widely anticipated. Such findings were echoed by the interviewed project beneficiaries. M-ERA.NET 3 (and the previous M-ERA.NETs) funded projects have collectively delivered, or are aiming to deliver, a broad set of scientific and technological advances, driven by the integration of materials development, characterisation, modelling and application-focused testing across international teams. The data and views gathered confirm that the network has been performing excellently in terms of the call identification process as well as the identified call topics, **filling in important gaps in advanced materials research**.

The network has produced extensive publication output and bibliometric analysis indicates strong performance in terms of citation attention (average of 21 citations / publication, with an average journal impact factor of 5.86) supporting the conclusion that the **programme contributes to scientific excellence** in advanced materials. The **interdisciplinary approach** is also noteworthy. The bibliometric analysis of the 1,017 publications that were reported as outputs of projects funded across all phases of M-ERA.NET, revealed three main cluster coming together (materials science, chemistry – biochemistry, and physics).

Innovation outputs were present and meaningful for a portfolio of projects that predominantly operated in mid-TRL ranges. Patenting activity was also identified across final project reports. In fact, a momentum seems to be growing after 2018 with more than 20 patents steadily being filed since. Protectable IP and proof-of-concept results were important outcomes for a subset of projects, including also SME partners. The evidence suggests that **transnational collaboration can accelerate invention and applied development** by assembling complementary capabilities and enabling access to facilities that may be difficult to secure within single-country funding contexts.

The findings underline the importance of M-ERA.NET 3 as a mechanism for deepening research excellence and international engagement, while also highlighting opportunities to provide more structured **pathways for commercialisation and market uptake** where appropriate. At the same time, industrial uptake is rather uneven, flagging the need for stronger mechanisms to improve translation of results into innovation outputs.

M-ERA.NET 3 is also **highly valued as a tool for policy coherence and alignment**, reducing fragmentation of national strategies. Its outputs, such as the [Materipedia](#) database, are recognised as assets that contribute

beyond the projects themselves. Its influence on high-level EU legislation, however, remains less visible. Another, often underappreciated, layer of impact concerns the network members themselves. Participation in M-ERA.NET has driven internal reforms, improved capacities, and modernised procedures in multiple funding organisations, showing strong institutional impact.

Industry and SME participation: strengths, constraints and implications

SME participation in M-ERA.NET has been **comparatively high** relative to other, comparable networks (e.g. ERA-MIN, FLAGERA and QuantERA), while **participation of large firms remains limited** across calls. While SME participation may be partly shaped by national participation rules, the programme's manageable project size, moderate administrative burden and mid-TRL orientation were described as features that make it more accessible to companies. **Barriers to stronger industry engagement** were repeatedly highlighted in interviews and were consistent with survey findings. These include long call and contracting timelines, state-aid and eligibility constraints, and limited proposal-writing capacity in SMEs.

The **impacts for participating industry, particularly SMEs**, appear most significant in relation to knowledge acquisition, enhanced scientific capabilities and strengthened international visibility. Commercial impacts, while achieved in some projects, were more variable. This, however, reflects the fact that most projects have achieved outputs that sit at TRL 3–5 where commercialisation pathways remain emergent. Nonetheless, the network has supported meaningful early-stage innovation and has also contributed to industrial readiness and future market potential by maturing technologies to a point where they can move into national funding programmes, Horizon Europe calls, or private R&D pipelines for further development. Overall, the evidence indicates that **M-ERA.NET 3 is effective in engaging SMEs and companies, strengthening their research capabilities, and supporting early-stage technological innovation**, even if the achievement of downstream commercial impacts typically requires additional funding for further development.

Added value and additionality, including counterfactual insights

Additionality and added value were assessed by comparing M-ERA.NET (all its phases) with other networks, establishing its European added value, and examining behavioural change and counterfactual effects. In the beneficiary survey, a clear majority rated M-ERA.NET as **better than, or the same, as other international networks across all dimensions**, with the strongest perceived advantages linked to collaboration and project structure, especially manageable project size, attractiveness to newcomers, and speed and flexibility of implementation. Respondents also tended to rate it favourably for lowering administrative burden, accessing high-quality expertise and facilities, and enabling ambitious research outcomes, while perceptions were more mixed on whole value-chain coverage, exploitation of results and project management. Interviews with the funding organisations emphasised that the programme's **thematic breadth** across advanced materials is a distinctive strength compared with narrower ERA-NETs, enabling smaller countries and regions to identify niches and participate, and supporting broad engagement including from non-European partners.

Behavioural additionality was evidenced most strongly in collaboration formation and increased engagement with international R&I collaboration. Survey results showed that the most common changes occurred in

forming new R&I consortia, and participation in other EU or international calls. In addition, M-ERA.NET projects increasingly integrate environmental, open science and wider RRI considerations into their research activities. For **unsuccessful applicants, the application process still produced benefits** for many, most often new collaborations, improved understanding of the application process, and insights into future R&D priorities.

Dissemination and impact visibility: a key weakness with strategic consequences

A recurring and prominent finding was that dissemination and external visibility are weaker than internal process quality. Interviews reported that, despite excellent projects, results were not consistently well-publicised, and the programme's contribution to industrial uptake and policy influence remained under-documented in the absence of systematic impact data and curated communication to non-academic audiences. This is a **strategic weakness** because it constrains the programme's ability to demonstrate value to policy and industry stakeholders and to translate scientific strength into broader innovation-system influence.

Strategic positioning and future outlook

The Commission acknowledges the value of M-ERA.NET 3 in policy alignment and foresees complementarity with initiatives such as IAM4EU and the forthcoming Advanced Materials Act. Structural complementarity and coordinated topic selection are viewed as essential. Partners express overwhelming support for its continuation and transformation into a more visible, policy-embedded structure in the next framework cycle. All respondents/interviewees agree that **M-ERA.NET is indispensable**. For large states it projects influence; for smaller ones it ensures visibility; for third countries it offers the only structured pathway into European collaboration. Its challenge is political: securing recognition commensurate with its demonstrated value.

The discussion during the Strategy Workshop, that was attended by M-ERA.NET 3 members and EC officials (December 2025), emphasised that M-ERA.NET is a timely connector in an EU landscape where advanced materials are central to technological sovereignty, the clean transition and economic security, but stronger "valley of death" bridging is needed to retain value and intellectual capital in Europe. Internationalisation should be selective and aligned with EU priorities, prioritising depth over breadth, with trusted partners and careful handling of sensitive cooperation areas. Stronger links to national and regional ecosystems are needed to improve uneven SME participation, shorten perceived complexity and timelines, and create post project valorisation pathways through matchmaking, transfer schemes or call design tweaks. Impact and infrastructure improvements should be pragmatic, including training on impact pathways and IPR, light post project monitoring, better pathways to later stage funding, and mapping and improving visibility, access and interoperability of Europe's fragmented infrastructure landscape.

Conclusions and priority recommendations for improvement

The assessment presents M-ERA.NET 3 as a **mature and high-performing transnational instrument** for advanced materials, with strong governance, wide geographical coverage and an operating model that

enables interdisciplinary collaboration through manageable consortia. The strongest evidenced impacts are **scientific excellence, capability building and durable international networks, with credible innovation outputs and meaningful SME benefits** emerging for a subset of projects. Challenges are not primarily linked to core programme design, but rather to persistent structural constraints and under-developed functions at the interface between research results and wider uptake-oriented initiatives.

The main constraints experienced by industry, particularly SMEs, relate to timelines, participation capacity and limited external dissemination of results. These are actionable areas for improvement, which were addressed by the interviewees with measures, such as improving connectivity between research results and industrial actors, stronger matchmaking and brokerage approaches and more visible success-story pipelines that translate technical results into narratives relevant to business, investors and policy audiences. Other operational improvement priorities emphasised the continued efforts to reduce friction arising from divergent national rules and timelines, and practical steps to address oversubscription and delays in project start where feasible.

The programme demonstrates a practical route to reduce fragmentation and widen participation in advanced materials, a **strategically important domain**, while supporting interdisciplinarity and capability building. The main improvements involve **raising the network's profile** and **communicating more clearly** so that its policy contributions are easier to understand. It also means **creating strong political links** to key current and upcoming EU strategies and policies.

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INTRODUCTION AND METHODOLOGY

This report is the final deliverable of the evaluation task assigned to AMANATIDOU/OPTIMAT by M-ERA.NET 3 in May 2025. Summarising the objectives of the task based on the terms of reference, the **primary goal of this assessment** was to evaluate the performance and impact of the M-ERA.NET 3 network, examining its success in achieving its objectives, specifically regarding joint transnational calls, network activities, thematic relevance to the needs and interests of the advanced material research community, and alignment with its mission and vision. The assessment also measured the network's impact on its target groups considering broader societal, economic, scientific and policy-related goals, including synergies with other innovation programs, alignment with Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe (HE) initiatives, and contributions to addressing global challenges. Additionally, it analysed the network's sustainability and long-term viability and sought to understand external and internal perceptions of M-ERA.NET 3. The assessment also benchmarked M-ERA.NET 3 outcomes against similar initiatives and provided recommendations for future improvements and the potential progression towards M-ERA.NET 4 and beyond.

Following the terms of reference, the assessment of M-ERA.NET 3 is an **ex-post, summative evaluation** using a **holistic approach with a forward-looking** orientation, that assesses M-ERA.NET 3's impact at various levels (national, European, scientific, policy, societal) as well as standard evaluation issues such as efficiency, effectiveness, added value, and additionality which is addressed in terms of program additionality (European added value) and changes in user behaviour, as well as the counterfactual element. The forward-looking orientation considers growth perspectives, network sustainability, and the positive impact of continued enhancement to position the M-ERA.NET 4 follow-up network within the partnership and EU initiatives landscape. Table 1 summarises the items and issues that were included in this final assessment.

Table 1: Final assessment issues²

Assessment items/ Issues	Including
Efficiency	Workplan and task implementation (resources – financial, human, other - time)
Effectiveness	Achievement of objectives including all levels (objectives hierarchy). Relevant contribution to higher level goals, relevant sectors (e.g. circular economy) and technologies. RRI approach.
Impact	Expected impact on policy, economy and society (policy alignment/ influence, economy & innovation, scientific, networking, capacity building, less-engaged countries, value chains, internationalisation, bibliometrics and patent analysis). Emerging impact pathway.
European added value / additionality	Leverage. Comparison of performance with other co-funded networks/initiatives and of impact depending on data availability/ comparability. Comparison of project/beneficiary data with those of H2020 and HE Cluster 4 calls depending on data availability/ comparability. Counterfactual: analysis of unsuccessful applicants.
Behavioural additionality	Changes in behaviour and/or perception of project beneficiaries and partnership members, including building long-standing collaborations.
Network performance, health, connectivity	Governance, management and coordination. Call implementation and evaluation. membership and financial commitments. International connectivity & Regional dimension. Dissemination and impact visibility.
Synergies with other EU initiatives	Examination of the synergy building approach in M-ERA.NET and its results, and the consequent positioning of M-ERA.NET 3 in the partnership landscape
Growth and future of M-ERA.NET	The growth and future dimension considering also the life-cycle approach.

Where possible, the design of the M-ERA.NET 3 survey (see Appendix A) retained questions that were comparable with those used in the previous Final Assessment of M-ERA.NET 2 (2022). This enables a high-level comparison of participant experience and perceived impacts across successive phases of the network, while recognising differences in timing, context, and programme maturity.

As shown in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, the methodology was based on a **mixed-methods design** combining a) desk research and extensive analysis of key performance indicator (KPI) data collected by M-ERA.NET 3 management team, b) interviews with M-ERA.NET 3 members and European Commission (EC) officers (17), extended interviews with project beneficiaries (40), and c) an online beneficiary survey that gathered 251 responses from successful applicants and 267 from unsuccessful applicants.³

² The connections of the evaluation issues with the logic frame of the evaluation and the typical questions asked under each of them is presented in [Selecting the evaluation questions – ERA-LEARN](#). The evaluation terminology that is used is presented in [the Glossary of the ERA-LEARN RIPE Toolkit](#).

³ Invitations to the survey were sent to 5,540 applicants that were unsuccessful at their latest efforts and 1,293 successful applicants. The returned emails (bounced, undelivered, etc.) were around 10% in each cohort

Table 2: Methodology

Method	Data/ Numbers
a) Desk research and extended KPI stats	M-ERA.NET , ERA-LEARN , eCORDA data
b) Interviews with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M-ERA,NET 3 members and EC officers • R&I project coordinators 	17 40
c) Online survey to project beneficiaries: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful R&I proposal applicants • Unsuccessful R&I proposal applicants (counterfactual analysis) 	251 responses (19.5% response rate) 267 responses (5% response rate)
+ Bibliometric and patent analysis	(192 relevant project reports for bibliometrics) (163 project reports patents)
+ Strategy workshop with M-ERA.NET 3 members and EC officers	around 40 participants

The process started with the refinement and finalisation of the assessment framework, including the intervention logic, key questions to be asked, and the areas of impact. Subsequent phases focused on identifying data needs, securing access to relevant datasets, and analysing existing monitoring information from M-ERA.NET 3, ERA-LEARN, and eCORDA, complemented by targeted interviews with the network management team and EC officials. This was followed by extensive primary research through beneficiary interviews and an online survey. The final stages integrated all quantitative and qualitative evidence into a synthesis that formulated the background material for a workshop involving the network members (around 40 participants) that discussed the legacy as well as the future strategy of M-ERA.NET. Throughout the process, iterative engagement with the M-ERA.NET 3 management team was achieved via regular online meetings and continuous feedback that ensured validation of findings and supported a robust, participatory evaluation process.

Concerning **analysis of the data**, the assessment refers to M-ERA.NET 3 taking place between 2021-2026. However, the data on the network membership and financial commitments goes back to 2012 to present a more comprehensive picture of the evolution of the network. The data in relation to the project financing and mobilisation of the research community are considered from the start of M-ERA.NET 2 (2016) providing an adequate timeframe (almost 10 years) to assess impacts. In some places the three phases of M-ERA.NET are mentioned, i.e. M-ERA.NET 1 (2012-2015), M-ERA.NET 2 (2016-2022) and M-ERA.NET 3 (2021-2026). Comparisons are made with three networks that are relevant or complementary to M-ERA.NET's scope, i.e. ERA-MIN, QuantERA and FLAGERA. In addition to the statistical analysis of the available M-ERA.NET data and the survey responses, information on publications and patents was retrieved from available final project

reports (across all M-ERA.NET phases) and bibliometric and patent analyses were carried out to identify any wider impacts delivered in terms of international networks and scientific collaboration.

ASSESSMENT OF M-ERA.NET 3

INTERVENTION LOGIC

Based on the review of M-ERA.NET 3 documentation and the interviews with the members of the consortium, the intervention logic of the network is depicted in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** The bottom line illustrates the **activities** ranging from those related to selecting, financing and supporting research and innovation projects (right hand side) to more **horizontal activities** connected to the consolidation of the participating programmes and actors, discussions about the future of the network and creating links with the wider EU research community and disseminating the project results.

The second layer is the **immediate outcomes** of the activities that correspond to the **short-term, operational objectives**. They include, for instance, the transfer of knowledge that occurs from the dissemination of the results of supported projects. At the same time, other network activities aim at the strategic programming of the joint activities of the network, its expansion in the EU and beyond and the strengthening the participation of certain actors like regions and EU13 countries⁴.

The third and fourth layers, accordingly, correspond to the **medium-term objectives** that may relate to further enhanced transnational collaboration and coordination of national/ regional programmes and, thus, the mobilisation of critical mass both in terms of funding, knowledge and human resources. This may then lead to reduced fragmentation and long-term collaboration between countries and regions, which are long-term, strategic objectives of the network.

The activities that support research and innovation projects will lead to enhanced cooperation between research actors in academia and other innovation organisations, while the knowledge produced will be addressing emerging areas and technologies while enhancing the capabilities of European industries.

In the **longer-term**, corresponding to the other strand of **high-level objectives** of the network, the enhanced scientific research and improved technological capabilities of industrial sectors in the area of advanced materials will contribute to the achievement of the European Green Deal objectives- also guided by the relevant strategies and action plans such as [Circular Economy Action Plan](#), the [EC communication “A clean planet for all”](#), and the [2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development](#) and its 17 Sustainable Development Goals in particular SDG 7 (“Affordable and clean energy”) and SDG 9 (“Industrial innovation and infrastructure”). At the same time, the long-term strategic cooperation among funding organisations at the national and regional levels will facilitate the reduction of the fragmentation of policies and strategies across countries, thus facilitating alignment and further strengthening the European Research Area.

It is also crucial to identify the **assumptions** underlying the intervention logic (Table). These assumptions, together with the intervention logic and objectives hierarchy, were discussed and agreed with the M-ERA.NET 3 management team and are shown below. It is in these assumptions that explanations can be found for both the successes and failures in the performance of M-ERA.NET 3. For instance, at the level of

⁴ Including Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia.

activities, those related to the expansion of the network will be successful if there is ample knowledge about networks and adequate resources to manage them. Activities in relation to dissemination and exploitation will lead to the medium-term objective of 'enhanced industrial capacities' if participation of industrial actors is enabled and internal organisation conditions exist to capitalise on the knowledge produced. The supported R&I projects will lead to effectively addressing emerging technological areas if there is interest to continue progressing on the innovation path and there is support for follow-on projects, where appropriate.

Creation of critical mass depends on the levels of funds committed (which can be a considerable share of national/ regional budgets) and the consolidation of research programmes depends on the flexibility to converge that exists at the national level. The long-term objectives such as durable collaboration and structure beyond the network life-time depends on continued political and financial support, while the strengthening of European leadership in the technology domain relies on both scientific excellence as well as the translation of the research outputs. This, in turn, relies on the quality of collaboration as well as the wider market, economic and competitive conditions in each particular technology application area that may facilitate or hinder the journey towards innovation.

Figure 1: Intervention Logic and Objectives Hierarchy of M-ERA.NET 3

Table 3: Assumptions behind the intervention logic for M-ERA.NET 3

In relation to the long-term strategic objectives	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is interest and commitment (political, financial) to make M-ERA.NET a durable structure beyond the periods of EU support. • The alignment and financial commitments are increasing over the years towards reduced fragmentation and increased convergence among countries/regions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The wider market, economic and competition conditions allow for increased interest to enhance capabilities in the given domain. • Collaboration is increasing among research and industry to the degree that it can contribute to building European tech leadership and enhanced scientific research.
In relation to the medium-term objectives	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The funds committed are a considerable share of national/regional budgets to create critical mass. • The required flexibility exists to align and converge the relevant programmes of countries/regions. • The M-ERA.NET calls are well informed on latest trends and do address cutting-edge emerging tech and application areas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The businesses that take part in M-ERA.NET projects have internal abilities to capitalise on the knowledge created and enhance their capabilities • They also have the interest to follow-up and progress down towards the innovation path - the projects are strategic enough for them. • There is support for the follow up of projects through M-ERA.NET or other trans-national or national programmes.
In relation to the short-term, operational objectives	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is ample knowledge about partnerships, and adequate resources - human, financial - and interest from non-EU countries, regions and EU-13 countries to take part. • There is interest and commitment (political, financial) to expand the network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The support provided for the exploitation of results is adequate to facilitate knowledge transfer. • The research and private actors (end-users) are brought together early enough to co-create the innovation generation. • There is access to the additional expertise (market, legal, etc.) required for exploitation early enough in the project

NETWORK PERFORMANCE, HEALTH AND CONNECTIVITY (INCLUDING EFFICIENCY)

This evaluation dimension considers the **external and internal views** of the network and each of its elements and operations, as well as its regional dimension. The network **openness and inclusiveness**, the **commitments** of its members, and the degree of sustained **collaboration and sustainability** are also features of its **health and connectivity**.

OVERALL PERCEPTIONS

M-ERA.NET 3 is almost universally described as one of the best-managed ERA-NETs by network partners and EC representatives and its **credibility, transparency, and professionalism** are repeatedly emphasised. Calls are attractive and oversubscribed, procedures are fair, and coordination is widely trusted. The network has become a benchmark, with its tools and methods emulated elsewhere.

The **motivations** driving participation in M-ERA.NET 3 reflect a complex **interplay of scientific ambition, policy alignment, capacity-building needs, and strategic positioning**. Across both European and non-European members, the rationale for joining the network has evolved over time, but core threads of internationalisation, critical mass building, and complementarity with Horizon Europe and national priorities remain central. The interviews reveal a range of perspectives – from large and well-resourced countries like Germany and Poland, to smaller Member States like Latvia and Slovenia, regional actors such as Saxony and Asturias, and to third-country participants such as Taiwan, Brazil/Sao Paulo, and Canada/Québec.

Several partners note that motivations have deepened over time. In Austria and Germany, what began as a way to pool resources has become an instrument for policy leadership. In Saxony, initial cautious participation grew into a core regional strategy, with rapidly rising budgets. In the early days of the ERA-NET instrument, Sweden pursued a broad strategy of joining many networks to maximise exposure and learning. Over time, as Sweden shifted towards a more selective strategy, M-ERA.NET was one of a small number that was retained due to its continuing relevance for materials science. Due to the lack of a dedicated national materials programme in recent years, however, Sweden's participation is limited to year-by-year decisions depending on budget availability. For Taiwan and Brazil/Sao Paulo, initial involvement as observers became long-term commitments once researchers recognised the opportunities for durable collaboration and access to European infrastructures.

At the European level, the EC initially saw ERA-NETs as coordination pilots; today it considers M-ERA.NET an instrumental alignment mechanism, feeding into consultations, strategic research and innovation agendas, and the Advanced Materials Technology Council.

GOVERNANCE, MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION OF THE NETWORK & FUNDED PROJECTS

Amongst **network partners**, there was praise for the coordination team for **responsive management and effective communication and coordination systems**, including IT. It was referred to by one partner as *“the best organised ERA-NET,”* whilst others commended the clarity and efficiency of communication. EC representatives view it more systemically as both a coordination mechanism and a contributor to EU-level policy discussions in advanced materials.

The **coordinators** of funded R&I projects that were **interviewed** as part of this assessment generally viewed M-ERA.NET’s governance and coordination framework as effective, well-structured and supportive of seamless transnational collaboration. The programme was frequently described as clear, responsive and professionally managed, with the Call Secretariat and national contact persons providing timely and reliable guidance throughout the proposal and implementation stages. Beneficiaries valued the transparency of communication channels and the accessibility of information, noting that call documentation, templates and the Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) section of the M-ERA.NET website were consistently well organised and easy to navigate.

At the **funded project level**, the beneficiaries that responded to the **online survey**⁵ were asked to rate various aspects of M-ERA.NET 3 management on a scale from 1 (Very poor) to 5 (Excellent). As shown in Figure 2, across almost all categories, the results show strongly positive perceptions, with the majority of respondents selecting 4 or 5. This indicates a generally **high level of satisfaction with both network-level processes and R&I project-level coordination**. Three areas stand out with exceptionally high ratings: **communication from the R&I project coordinator, quality of collaboration within the R&I project consortium, and monitoring and reporting requirements**. These categories received the highest number of “5” ratings (131, 131, and 99 respectively) and very few low ratings, suggesting that project beneficiaries view the collaborative and administrative dimensions of project delivery very favourably.

Overall, the online results present a strong endorsement of M-ERA.NET 3’s management processes. Respondents perceive both network-level operations and project-level coordination as **well organised, transparent, and conducive to successful collaboration**.

Figure 2: Quality of Management

Project beneficiaries report very high satisfaction with M-ERA.NET management, particularly communication, collaboration and monitoring processes

⁵ 251 successful applicants and 267 unsuccessful applicants.

There was, however, a recurrent theme concerning the **challenges** that are inherent in the **decentralised funding of joint calls** in M-ERA.NET 3. Differences in national procedures, such as unaligned project start dates, variable co-funding rules and the requirement in some countries to submit separate applications to national funding bodies, were cited as sources of administrative complexity. Several project coordinators highlighted that these issues occasionally impacted on their ability to effectively and efficiently plan projects and there were recommendations for greater harmonisation or a stronger central coordinating role, particularly during project initiation. Nonetheless, most participants regarded the overall governance approach as proportionate, pragmatic and enabling, with M-ERA.NET 3 striking a balance between jointly coordinated calls and national accountability mechanisms that preserves funding flexibility.

CALL IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

At the level of the **M-ERA.NET 3 consortium**, the members consistently praised as a strong point the design and implementation of calls. The two-stage process, where centralised international peer review at stage one was introduced in 2023, is widely valued for filtering proposals fairly and transparently. The dynamism of call topics, which are updated annually to reflect both national/regional inputs and EU priorities, was also emphasised. This responsiveness was considered one of M-ERA.NET 3’s strengths compared to other networks with more rigid thematic agendas.

In a similar vein, the R&I **project coordinators** consistently praised the **quality of call implementation**, describing the process as clear, predictable and well aligned with the needs of mid-TRL materials research. The two-stage application procedure was widely appreciated for reducing workload and enabling strategic refinement of proposals, while the level of administrative burden was considered appropriate and far lighter than that associated with large EU framework programmes.

As shown in Figure 3, the project beneficiaries that responded to the online survey rated call design and implementation as high. **Quality of call topic definition, ease of proposal submission, and usefulness and transparency of evaluation** all received strong positive scores, with most respondents rating them as “4” or “5”.

Figure 3: Quality of Call Implementation and Evaluation

Applicants generally view the call implementation and evaluation process positively

Regarding clarity of call documents, as shown in Figure 4, the distribution of responses shows overwhelmingly positive perceptions, with the largest number of respondents selecting ratings toward the upper end of the scale. The most frequently selected scores were eight (92 responses), nine (41 responses), and ten (35 responses), indicating that **the majority of participants found the documentation to be clear, well-structured, and easy to interpret.**

Figure 4: Quality of Call Documentation

Call documentation is widely viewed as clear and helpful, with most applicants able to understand the requirements and prepare proposals effectively

The contact persons within the national funding agencies, whose role is to provide advice to applicants, were again highlighted by project coordinators as being important due to the support they provided during the application process, offering constructive support and helping to ensure proposals were compliant with call requirements.

Online survey respondents were asked to rate the **sufficiency of guidance and support** received from three sources: national M-ERA.NET 3 contact persons, M-ERA.NET 3 call secretariat, and R&I project consortium partners, on a scale from 1 (not helpful at all) to 5 (very helpful). The results show (in Figure 5) a broadly positive pattern, with most respondents reporting moderate to high levels of support across all three categories.

- Support from other consortium partners received the strongest ratings overall, with 97 respondents selecting 4 and 91 selecting 5, indicating that peer-to-peer collaboration within project consortia was consistently regarded as highly supportive
- Support from national/regional contact persons also received largely positive evaluations. For contact persons, 70 respondents rated support as 4 and 74 as 5, with relatively few low scores.

- Similarly, support from R&I project coordinators showed a concentration of responses at the upper end of the scale (76 respondents rated 4; 54 rated 5).

Figure 5: Guidance and Support

Applicants report strong satisfaction with the guidance and support provided, particularly from national contact points and consortium partners.

Based on feedback from the interviews with project coordinators, the **evaluation process** was generally regarded as **fair, rigorous and technically credible**. Project coordinators reported that application reviewers demonstrated good domain expertise. A small number of project coordinators, however, identified **occasional challenges**, including inconsistent reviewer assessments, and strict formal checks. As a result, there were suggestions for improved moderation between reviewers and clearer guidance on formatting requirements.

Other challenges and issues highlighted by network partners included long contractual timelines (7 - 8 months from submission of full proposals to contracts being in place), heavy workloads, and occasional delays in national eligibility checks.

This is consistent with the results from the online survey. As shown in Figure 2: Quality of Management, **sufficiency of financial resources and the overall call timeline** received higher numbers of “3” ratings and a more noticeable spread across the scale. This suggests that, while respondents are generally satisfied with funding and timelines, these aspects are **less universally praised and may reflect constraints outside the direct control of M-ERA.NET 3**, such as national funding limitations or different decision-making schedules among participating agencies.

Respondents to the online survey (project applicants) were asked whether they received feedback on their proposal following the evaluation process. The results show (Figure 6) that while most applicants reported receiving feedback, the perceived depth and usefulness of this feedback varied. A total of 151 respondents indicated that the feedback received was limited in detail, making this the most common response. A further 82 respondents reported receiving detailed and useful feedback, while 37 respondents stated that they had not received feedback.

It is important to note that evaluation feedback is provided to the project coordinator / lead applicant via the network’s IT system and since 2023 all proposals automatically receive their evaluation reports. The survey findings should, therefore, be interpreted as **reflecting perceived access to and usefulness of feedback among individual applicants**, rather than differences in whether feedback is formally provided.

Figure 6: Feedback on the Proposal

Most applicants receive feedback on their proposals, but many perceive it as limited in detail and usefulness

These results suggest that although the evaluation process ensures transparency and systematic provision of feedback, there is considerable variation within project consortia on how useful it is perceived to be for understanding evaluation outcomes or improving future applications. In particular, the fact that “limited feedback” is the modal category indicates that many respondents feel that the information received does not provide sufficient guidance for proposal improvement. At the same time, the substantial group reporting detailed and useful feedback demonstrates that strong practice exists and that the evaluation reports can provide valuable insights when effectively communicated and interpreted.

Nonetheless, the dominant view amongst both project participants and network members was that implementation and evaluation processes delivered a high-quality, researcher-friendly experience while maintaining efficiency and transparency across participating countries. **The credibility of the evaluation**

process was considered to be one of the network’s strongest assets.

DISSEMINATION AND IMPACT VISIBILITY

Dissemination was found to be one of the weaker aspects of M-ERA.NET 3 performance. Interviews with M-ERA.NET 3 members highlighted that, while internal processes are excellent, **external visibility is weak**. Several partners argue for stronger, systematic connections between projects and policy and business audiences (via conferences, knowledge communities, and curated success-story pipelines, for example) so that learning circulates beyond the immediate research teams. As noted by some interviewees,

“despite excellent projects, their results are not well-publicised”.

Without effective dissemination and systematic impact data, the network’s contribution to industrial uptake and policy influence remained under-documented. The EC also acknowledged that while M-ERA.NET 3 has provided valuable inputs, its project-level impacts are not sufficiently highlighted at policy level compared to more politically visible partnerships.

PARTICIPATING COUNTRIES AND REGIONS IN THE NETWORK

M-ERA.NET has evolved from a network of 24 countries (including 11 regions) in M-ERA.NET 1, to 30 countries including 12 regions in M-ERA.NET 2, and 35 countries including 14 regions in M-ERA-NET 3. The number of countries participating in network calls has been steady, at around 25, since 2012, while the cofunded call in 2021 clearly attracted most of the network members. In addition, the share of regions participating in the network calls has been consistently above 25% since 2016, with a peak in 2019 (35%).

Figure 7: Number of national agencies and share of regional agencies participating in M-ERA.NET calls

From a network of 24 countries (including 11 regions) in M-ERA.NET 1, to 35 countries including 14 regions in M-ERA-NET 3

effectively. The interviews with the M-ERA.NET 3 members revealed a network that is widely considered collegial, resilient, and adaptive. At the same time, its operation is marked by asymmetries: a core group of large, well-resourced and experienced agencies drives much of the work, while smaller or regional actors participate with lighter operational footprints due to lack of inhouse resources. This asymmetry is not perceived as exclusionary, however. Instead, it is seen as pragmatic: those with more resources lead, while others still benefit from inclusion.

Across almost all members' interviews, one of the most striking findings was the **high level of trust** among partners. Agencies described the culture of M-ERA.NET 3 as open, constructive, and solution oriented. Disagreements over eligibility, budgets, or evaluation are usually resolved through negotiation rather than confrontation. Slovenia characterised the atmosphere as one of “*collegial problem-solving*”, where even politically driven shifts could be accommodated flexibly. France and Portugal similarly stressed that while frustrations occur, trust in the network’s governance and the fairness of its processes remains strong.

This trust is especially important given the network’s size. With over forty partners from nearly all EU Member States, many associated countries, and several global participants (including South Korea, Taiwan, Canada, Brazil, and South Africa) M-ERA.NET 3 is the broadest ERA-NET ever established. The fact that it has maintained collegiality and operational smoothness is often cited as proof of its institutional health.

Over the 14 calls, the number of participating countries has been around 25 or above since 2012 (except in 2020) with numbers higher for M-ERA.NET 3 (calls 2021-2025). There is a core of 11 countries including 5 EU14 members states (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Spain, Luxemburg), 4 EU13 countries (Hungary, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland), 1 associated country (Türkiye) and 1 non-EU country (Taiwan) that have participated in all 14 M-ERA.NET calls since 2012.

Figure 8: Number of EU13, EU14 and non-EU member countries participating in M-ERA.NET calls

An inclusive and stable network

The number of EU13 countries participating in calls has been steady, at 11, since 2021 (EC co-funded joint call) after a decrease to 7 in 2020. The non-EU member countries participating in calls has increased considerably from 4 in the first phase to 8 in the second, and eventually to 11 in M-ERA.NET 3. In relation to the non-cofunded calls, at least 15 national agencies have taken part since 2012, except the 2020 call, and that has been an increase to 20 or above in the 2023 and 2024 calls. The number of regional agencies that participated in the non-cofunded calls of the first phase was between 6-8. This rose to 8-12 in the second phase calls and stabilised at around 10 in M-ERA.NET 3. Overall, the network shows a good record both in terms of inclusivity, stability in the number of participating countries in the calls and a rise in participation of all country groups (EU13, EU14 as well as non-EU MS).

FINANCIAL COMMITMENTS

The current phase of M-ERA.NET (3) included one call (2021) that was co-funded by the EC with €11.002.643 as top-up and €58.901.973 as partners' contributions. In the previous phase, M-ERA.NET 2, there was another call (2016) that was also co-funded by the EC with €8.995.362 and €23.263.438 as partners' contributions. All other calls were solely financed by the national and regional agencies. The **commitments** made by countries and regions for the network calls have been steadily rising from €114 million in M-ERA.NET 1, to €134 million in M-ERA.NET 2 and €215 million in M-ERA.NET 3. It is also evident that the calls that are co-funded by the EC (2016 and 2021) attract higher commitments from countries and regions. While the commitments of the EU14 countries have fluctuated over the years, those of the EU13 show a steady increase since 2017. The highest value of total commitments by EU13 countries reached €13.464.418 in the 2021 call.

Figure 9: Commitments from funding agencies in M-ERA.NET calls (€ million)

Initial commitments: from €114 million (M-ERA.NET 1) to €215 million in M-ERA.NET 3

USE OF COMMITTED BUDGETS AND ACTUAL FUNDING

The use of committed budgets has ranged from an overestimation of the required funds leading to underspending for most of the participating countries in M-ERA.NET 1 (all calls), to 17 out of the 30 countries spending around 100% or exceeding their initial commitments in M-ERA.NET 2 (all calls), and to a more balanced picture under M-ERA.NET 3 (all calls) with more than half of the countries (19/35) spending between 100%-150% of their initial commitments.

Regarding the actual funding of projects, as expected, the call that was co-funded by the EC in 2021 attracted more funds reaching around €70 million (including the EU top-up), which is more than two times the funding reached by the previous co-funded call (2016: €30 million). It is also interesting to see that the calls after 2021 also present large amounts of actual funding (€ 28-44 million). Across any call, most of the funds come from countries such as Germany, Poland, Norway, Spain, Austria, Belgium, as well as Czechia and Luxembourg. EU13 participation has been rising in both membership and financial commitment over the years, i.e. from around € 8 million in M-ERA.NET 2 to € 12-14 million in M-ERA.NET 3.

Figure 10: Actual funding per country group (incl. EU top-up) in M-ERA.NET calls (€ million)

(*) 2025 call: still planned (not actual) funding

Steady increase of actual funding (incl. EU top-up) especially for EU13 countries

INTERNATIONAL CONNECTIVITY

M-ERA.NET 3 stands out as the **largest and most internationally connected** ERA-NET, supporting transnational research and innovation in advanced materials. Interviews conducted with national, regional, and third-country funders reveal a network that combines operational excellence with significant policy and

institutional impacts. Yet its success is tempered by limited industrial uptake, and a lack of political visibility within the Horizon Europe landscape.

Across all survey respondents, internationalisation is the **dominant motivation**. Large funders such as Austria and Germany view M-ERA.NET as a vehicle for embedding their already-strong materials communities into wider European and global networks. Smaller partners, such as Latvia, Slovenia, or regional partners such as Saxony, and newer Member states, such as Romania, see it as a way of overcoming peripherality and limited domestic resources. For third-country participants (e.g. Taiwan, Brazil, Canada), the network constitutes their first structured entry into EU framework collaboration, enhancing visibility and legitimacy.

Some **absences** were noted in the current phase during the interviews with the network members, including the Netherlands, the UK, and the US, as gaps in strategic coverage. Taiwan suggested deepening ties with Japan and South Korea. Brazil expressed interest in involving other Latin American countries. Overall, as noted by the interviewees, very few other ERA-NETs have successfully integrated not only nearly all EU and associated states, but also global players. Portugal's FCT similarly valued the inclusion of partners from Brazil and Taiwan, which would not be possible under standard Horizon Europe calls. The members of the consortium repeatedly described this global reach as a comparative advantage.

EFFICIENCY

Efficiency is usually evaluated in terms of **resources spent** (financial, human, time, other) for the **operation of the network**, answering questions like “to what extent has the programme delivered its intended outputs and outcomes in a timely and cost-effective way (compared to other examples if possible)”? As data was not accessed regarding the actual resources spent on the operation of the comparable networks, efficiency is assessed based on the views of M-ERA.NET 3 members during interviews.

The interviews with the M-ERA.NET 3 members shed ample light on how the network compares to other networks in terms of operation and management. As many of the members noticed, M-ERA.NET 3 was far **more professional in its operations**. Brazil's FAPESP, likewise, stressed that the clarity and legitimacy of M-ERA.NET 3's call process was better than in many bilateral or multilateral initiatives. M-ERA.NET (across multiple phases) also provides greater stability and fewer funding mismatches, unlike ERA-LAC or Belmont Forum, where misalignments often leave good projects unfunded. Austria's FFG and Germany's PtJ emphasised that M-ERA.NET's IT tools, evaluation procedures, and governance models have been replicated by other initiatives, including QuantERA, the upcoming Raw Materials Partnership, and other thematic networks.

The M-ERA.NET 3 network members also noted that the **administrative workload** of M-ERA.NET is **broadly similar to other partnerships** (heavier for some than others but overall manageable) and that coordination costs are no higher than elsewhere. By comparison, ERA-NETs such as ERA-MIN or QuantERA are smaller, less inclusive, and have less regular calls. While they have their strengths, such as ERA-MIN's tight connection to raw materials policy and QuantERA's close link to quantum technology agenda, their scope and breadth of participation are narrower. M-ERA.NET 3's governance, by contrast, has proven capable of handling 40+ partners across continents. This sheer **scale is unique**, and it is **operationally impressive** that

the network continues to function smoothly despite such complexity.

EFFECTIVENESS

Effectiveness refers to the **achievement of objectives at all levels**, i.e. short-term / operational, mid-term, and long-term strategic. Following the intervention logic and the objectives' hierarchy (cf. **Fehler! V erweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**) and starting from the short-term, operational objectives, the assessment of effectiveness needs to include the **level of mobilisation** of the research community in relation to the launched calls, the **levels of participation** and different **types of participation** (countries, roles, gender dimension and interdisciplinarity). An analysis of the **outcomes of the supported projects**, addressing the medium-term objectives, is also required which is complemented by an exploration of various **types of impacts** touching upon medium- and long-term objectives.

MOBILISATION OF THE R&I COMMUNITY

Excluding the two calls that were co-funded by the EC (2016 in M-ERA.NET 2 and 2021 in M-ERA.NET 3), where participation is higher, as expected (232 applications in 2016 and 493 in 2021), the network presents a steady increase in relation to the number of submitted proposals as well as the number of individual applicants.

Figure 11: Number of submitted proposals and of individual applicants per call

The mobilisation of the scientific community has been steadily increasing

The highest number of projects recommended for funding were in the calls that were EC-cofunded (2016 and 2021). Numbers were steady in the 2022 and 2023 calls (between 40-50 projects), whereas the two last calls have settled around 30 projects. The decrease often happens because some countries have lower success rates compared to others. It is also partly due to gaps created in the selection list as a result of some countries running out of funds before they are able to support all their highly-ranked projects.

In addition, the number of submitted proposals increases faster than the number of supported projects, which results in a lower success rate⁶, i.e. from around 20% in 2016/17 to less than 10% in 2024 and 2025. Indeed, the high oversubscription rates were noted by some M-ERA.NET 3 members during the interviews.

Certain mitigation measures have been put in place, such as the centralised international peer review that was implemented at stage one of the evaluation process in 2023. Some interviewees highlighted that this reform reduced the oversubscription problem at later stages. In addition, measures have been put in place at the national level. For example, Germany’s PtJ refines the scope of each call topic to reduce the volume of proposals. This approach manages system overload associated with broader calls, but it also introduces trade-offs, as narrowly defined calls may result in available funding not being fully utilised.

Figure 12: Number of projects and success rate per call

The increasing number of proposals has resulted in lowering success rates (related to pre-proposals), although measures are taken to manage high oversubscription.

Based on ERA-LEARN data, compared to other networks such as ERA-MIN, QuantERA and FLAG-ERA, M-ERA.NET has increasingly attracted more countries, having been launching calls, on an annual basis, since 2012. This created a continuum that has led to more committed funds over the years, and thus more projects that account for significantly larger funding. In particular, M-ERA.NET (all phases) has supported **around 5 times the number of projects that the other networks** have funded over their existence, at **total project costs of around €520 million**. This is more than **five times the respective total project costs** of QuantERA (all phases), the second largest network in this regard, as ERA-MIN (all phases) and FLAGERA (all phases) present much lower values. Further details are provided in Table 4.

⁶ Defined as the number of full proposals recommended for funding divided by the number of total number of pre-proposals.

Table 4: Comparative features of M-ERA.NET and other networks (all phases)

Network	Requested EU contribution	No of participating countries (last phase)	Duration	Years	No. calls	No. projects	Average no projects/call	Total costs of funded projects	Average size of funded consortia
Total ERA-MIN	€11 mio	29	2011-2025	16	8	88	11	€94 mio	5.85
Total FLAGERA	€14 mio	28	2013-2024	15	6	93	15	€32 mio	4.84
Total QuantERA	€26 mio	33	2016-2026	12	5	101	20	€103 mio	5.44
Total M-ERA.NET	€30 mio	35	2012-2026	16	14	481	32	€520 mio	4.51

Source: ERA-LEARN, Cordis

M-ERA.NET excels compared to other networks and it reaches 50% of the number of projects supported under relevant calls in both Horizon framework programmes.

In addition, based on eCORDA data, the number of **projects funded by M-ERA.NET (all phases, i.e. 2012 – 2025) reaches almost 50% (49.9%) the number of projects funded under all relevant calls in H2020 and Horizon Europe**. M-ERA.NET supported 481 in 14 years, while the relevant calls in the H2020 and Horizon Europe funded 963 projects (between 2014-2025).⁷

The **average size of the project consortia** is similar across the different networks ranging from 4.5 partners (FLAG-ERA) to 5.8 (ERA-MIN). This is much lower than the average size of Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs) supported under Horizon 2020 (average of 15 partners) or Horizon Europe (14.5) thereby filling a gap that is not funded elsewhere. This was **much praised by the interviewees** as they considered that smaller and more manageable consortia enabled true collaboration and real blending of expertise under interdisciplinary approaches.

SME AND INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION

The evidence suggests that the calls that were topped up by the EC (2016 and 2021) had a higher level of participation by SMEs, in addition to universities and research organisations. The number of SMEs in successful projects is higher than in any other call. Furthermore, SMEs are the most common type of organisations to be self-funded applicants, with an increasing number included in applications under M-ERA.NET calls since 2020 as demonstrated in Figure 13.

⁷ 514 RIA / IA projects in NMBP calls in H2020, 370 RIA / IA projects in Cluster 4 and 79 projects in the battery-related calls in Cluster 5 under Horizon Europe.

Figure 13: Number of different types of participants per call in successful projects

In M-ERA.NET 3 calls, for countries such as Austria, Denmark, and Sweden, 1 in 2 project participants (around 50%) is either an SMEs or large company.⁸ This is comparable to the Research and Innovation Actions supported under the Horizon Europe Cluster 4 or the Horizon 2020 relevant calls⁹, where around 1 in 2 project partners are private commercial entities.

The participation of large firms, however, is rather limited across the calls. While M-ERA.NET is considered to have engaged industry at a less than desired level, the network still has a higher percentage of large company and SME participants compared to other networks.

Table 5: Shares of large companies and SMEs in projects funded by M-ERA.NET and other networks

	Private - large company	Private - SME
ERA-MIN	10.64%	20.21%
ERA-MIN 2	11.11%	24.07%
ERA-MIN3	14.15%	20.49%
FLAG-ERA	0.69%	2.07%
FLAG-ERA II	3.23%	5.38%
FLAG-ERA III	1.02%	2.55%
M-ERA.NET	7.77%	28.40%
M-ERA.NET 2	8.59%	26.04%
M-ERA.NET 3	4.94%	22.81%
QuantERA	0.00%	1.36%
QuantERA II	0.93%	9.35%

Source: ERA-LEARN database

⁸ This reflects the national conditions for participation where SME partner might be obligatory for example.

⁹ LEIT-ADVMAT, LEIT-ANDMANU, and LEIT-NMP.

SME participation in all M-ERA.NET phases is higher than in ERA-MIN, FLAG-ERA, and QuantERA. In contrast, the share of large company participation ranks second, following the levels observed in ERA-MIN

However, **barriers persist in relation to the participation of SMEs and large companies.** The members of the network who were interviewed identified these as including: a lack of proposal-writing expertise in companies; long timelines discouraging industry; and state-aid rules restricting funding flexibility compared to Horizon Europe programmes. Suggestions to mitigate this include separate ranking lists for industrial vs academic projects or making company participation mandatory in some calls, although the latter may bring challenges to funding agencies that can only fund public academic actors. Dissemination is also essential for mobilising SMEs, who are often persuaded to engage in innovation activities by visible peer examples rather than abstract policy arguments.

PROJECT COORDINATORS

In M-ERA.NET 3, the countries with the highest share of coordinators¹⁰ are Germany, Spain, and Austria followed by Norway and Finland¹¹. Interestingly, there are cases like Poland and France where the share of coordinators is relatively low despite the large number of projects. However, this changes from one M-ERA.NET phase to another. In M-ERA.NET 2 the top countries in coordinators' shares were Germany (66.67%) and Austria (57.89%), Norway (62.5%), Slovenia (60%) and Italy (58.82%)¹².

Figure 14: Share of coordinators across the total number of projects per country in M-ERA.NET 3

In addition to Germany and Austria, smaller research communities such as Slovenia assume leading roles in M-ERA.NET 3 projects more frequently than most other countries. By contrast, countries such as Poland, France, and Czechia tend to take on these roles less often.

¹⁰ Defined as the number of coordinators divided by the number of projects that a country has.

¹¹ Excluding Portugal and Luxembourg due to the very low number of projects.

¹² Excluding Ireland with only 3 projects.

GENDER DIMENSION

Over time, a slight increase is notable in the numbers for both women coordinators and project partners from the second phase of the network to the third, i.e. from 56 women project coordinators in M-ERA.NET 2 to 77 in M-ERA.NET 3, and from 109 women project partners in M-ERA.NET 2 to 187 in M-ERA.NET 3. In addition, the highest shares of women coordinators are from countries such as, Germany, Luxemburg and Italy as well as Austria and Portugal.

Figure 15: Number of female and non-female coordinators and partners across M-ERA.NET 2 and 3

Improved gender balance in M-ERA.NET 3

FOSTERING INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

Feedback from project coordinators indicated that **interdisciplinarity is a defining characteristic** of M-ERA.NET 3 projects. This manifests consistently in two complementary ways:

1. Integration of multiple scientific and technological fields within a single research approach
2. Collaboration across diverse stakeholder types, including universities, research institutes, SMEs, and in some cases end-users.

The **impacts of this interdisciplinary approach are substantial**, shaping scientific outputs, technological progress, and the durability of collaborations.

Analysis of the feedback from project coordinators interviewed as part of this evaluation indicated that most projects combined multiple scientific domains as an inherent requirement of materials research. Many coordinators explicitly stated that achieving their objectives would have been impossible without integrating multiple technical fields. These included, for example theoretical modelling, materials synthesis and characterisation, materials chemistry, biology, photonics and digital technologies.

“The approach was deliberately interdisciplinary, combining powder metallurgy, casting, SLM/SLMS, laser texturing, biocompatibility testing, tribology, and device packaging.”

Although the majority of projects were fully academic, with only partners from universities, a number included other stakeholder types, such as research institutes and industry (mainly SMEs), either as project partners, members of advisory boards or in-kind contributors providing, for example, materials or access to

equipment or facilities.

This interdisciplinary approach helped projects overcome challenges that arose. For instance, modelling partners informed material redesign, industrial partners validated the feasibility of using materials or components in specific applications, and partners with expertise in biological sciences refined material functionality in medical applications. This, in turn, enabled consortia to progress technologies from very low technology readiness levels (TRL 1-2) towards TRL 4-6, often producing demonstrators, validated laboratory devices (biosensors, hydrogen-production catalysts) or application-ready materials. **These advances would not have been possible if contributions from chemistry, physics, engineering, computation, and end-user testing had not been combined.**

Another recurring theme was that these interdisciplinary approaches fostered strong working relationships amongst partners and **sparked new ideas for further research** into new potential applications of project outputs. This, subsequently, led to multiple follow up proposals (such as Horizon Europe, [EIC Pathfinder](#), national calls) and ongoing collaborations beyond the project lifetime.

A **bibliometric analysis** was also undertaken to provide a more detailed understanding of **international connectivity and interdisciplinarity enabled by the network**. This involved an analysis of the 1,017 publications that were reported as outputs of projects funded across all phases of M-ERA.NET (at the time of this final assessment being undertaken). This reveals where research activity clusters around key topics and where interdisciplinary connections are emerging, illustrating how the network supports integration across different fields, as shown in Figure 16.

Targeted NANOMedicine to reverse FIBrosis in ischemic cardiomyopathies - NANOFIB

This consortium combined nanotechnology, molecular biology, analytical chemistry, regenerative medicine, and device engineering across partners in Spain and Poland. This breadth enabled the co-development of new enzymatic inks and electrochemical biosensors with biological groups producing and characterising enzymes, nanomaterials teams designing functional interfaces, and an SME integrating these components into prototype devices. The coordinator noted that the project “*bridg[ed] nanotechnology, molecular biology, regenerative medicine, and pre-clinical translational models,*” and that complementary expertise was essential to progress the technology.

Figure 16: Co-occurrence network of themes and concepts in M-ERA.NET 3 publications. An interactive version of this network is available by clicking on this [link](#)

Participation in M-ERA.NET 3 projects is a strong enabler of interdisciplinary approaches to the development and application of new advanced materials in wide-ranging technology domains

This co-occurrence network of science and engineering themes and concepts across all phases of M-ERA.NET shows a strong focus on materials science, engineering, nanotechnology, and chemistry. Three main thematic clusters are clearly visible, namely, a materials science cluster (shown in cyan), a chemistry – biochemistry cluster (shown in blue), and a physics cluster (shown in red). Other smaller clusters include optoelectronics (shown in green) and an electrochemistry focused cluster (shown in yellow/green). These clusters align with the evolving core priorities across all M-ERA.NET phases and represent the areas with the highest numbers of publications.

EU13 COUNTRIES’ PARTICIPATION IN PROJECTS

It is evident that calls that are co-funded by the EC result in more projects. This is valid for all country cohorts (EU13, EU14 and non-EU countries), although the largest benefit is with the EU14 group. Considering EU13, participants from these countries were involved in 40 projects in the 2016 call, double the number in the following year. While the 2019 call was also quite successful with 41 projects involving

EU13 participants, the 2021 EC co-funded call resulted in 58 projects with EU13 participants being funded. This was repeated in 2022 (56 projects) but the numbers have been slightly decreasing since. Of the EU13 countries, those that have had the highest number of successful projects over the years (2016-2025) are Poland (26%), Czechia (9%), Latvia (7%) and Romania and Slovenia (6%).

Figure 17: Number of projects per country group

The calls co-funded by the EC result in more projects for all country cohorts (EU13, EU14 and non-EU countries), although the largest benefit is with the EU14 group.

The proportion of EU13 coordinators within the overall coordinator pool appears to be influenced more by the specific call year than by the availability of EC co-funding, ranging from 14% in 2023 to 45% in 2024. Across the 2016–2024 period, the share of EU13 partners consistently remains within the 30–40% range.

M-ERA.NET 3 OUTCOMES

Survey respondents were asked what outcomes had been achieved as a result of their involvement in M-ERA.NET 3 projects, selecting from a broad list of scientific, collaborative, and innovation-related impacts. The results show strong evidence of meaningful outputs across multiple dimensions of research and collaboration. As shown in Figure 18, several outcomes show a high proportion of “Yes” responses, particularly those associated with knowledge generation and international cooperation.

Figure 18: Project outcomes

M-ERA.NET 3 projects most strongly deliver international collaboration, knowledge exchange and scientific outputs.

The most commonly achieved outcomes include:

- Access to new international research institutions or universities (192 respondents)
- Access to new know-how (168 respondents)
- Peer-reviewed joint publications (140 respondents)
- Creation of new scientific methods or data (132 respondents)

These findings align with the core objectives of M-ERA.NET 3 in fostering cross-border research collaboration and strengthening scientific capacity.

Outcomes related to **collaboration with industry and applied innovation show a more mixed pattern**. While substantial numbers of respondents reported access to new international industry partners (125 respondents) and new or improved products, services, or processes (100 respondents), these categories also show higher proportions of “partially” or “no” responses, suggesting that innovation outputs are being achieved but at a more variable rate across projects. Similarly, long-term outcomes, such as long-term recruitment of staff, presentations to stakeholders or policymakers, and publications for non-academic audiences display a balanced distribution of “yes,” “partially,” and “no,” indicating uneven realisation of these outcomes among participants.

This pattern is consistent with the mid-TRL focus of M-ERA.NET 3, where projects are primarily expected to strengthen collaboration, generate knowledge and advance technologies towards application, while commercial, policy and long-term workforce outcomes and impacts typically emerge over a longer timeframe

beyond the project duration.

More specialised or **downstream outcomes** (such as patents, contributions to standards, and spin-out creation) were **achieved far less frequently**, with the majority of respondents selecting “no” or “not applicable.” This pattern is common in collaborative R&I programmes where intellectual property generation and commercialisation activities often occur beyond the immediate project timeframe or are relevant only to specific types of research partners.

Overall, the results demonstrate that **M-ERA.NET 3 is highly effective in delivering its primary goals of enhancing international research cooperation, generating new knowledge, and supporting joint scientific outputs.**

These findings were reflected in the feedback from the project coordinators that were interviewed.

Building Transnational and International Networks and Collaboration

Participation in M-ERA.NET 3 projects consistently enabled research organisations to **extend and deepen their international networks in ways that would not have been achievable through national funding alone.** Across the interviews, coordinators reported that the programme provided a structured and practical mechanism for identifying and engaging partners with complementary expertise in other countries, often leading to new collaborations that strategically strengthened their research capabilities.

For many, especially those in smaller research systems such as Lithuania, Luxembourg, Norway and Portugal, the opportunity to work transnationally filled gaps in domestic capacity by opening access to specialised knowledge, advanced methodologies and diverse scientific perspectives. In several cases, initial collaborations built through M-ERA.NET 3 have evolved into **long-term partnerships** that continued into new proposals under other European programmes, demonstrating durable connectivity beyond the grant period.

Existing bilateral relationships were also **expanded into wider European networks** when partners invited additional institutions to join or identified new collaborators through M-ERA.NET online tools such as the partner search facility on the network website. The programme, therefore, functioned not merely as a funding source but as a **platform for sustained international engagement, strengthening the integration of national research communities within the broader European Research Area and, in some cases, extending**

International Connectivity

Spain–Romania–Brazil: each partner contributed a unique capability (3D printing, catalyst synthesis, photocatalysis testing), creating a capability chain unavailable within one country.

Lithuania–Latvia–Slovenia: partners exchanged samples instead of outsourcing tests, allowing all key analyses to remain “within the consortium” and making the project more integrated and cost-effective.

Slovenia–Latvia–Taiwan: combined theoretical modelling and catalytic performance testing, enabling “15 joint publications” and long-term cooperation.

collaborations to global partners such as South Africa, Brazil, and Japan. Through this network expansion, M-ERA.NET 3 enhanced the strategic reach of participating organisations, increased their competitiveness in future transnational funding calls, and supported the development of research ecosystems that are more interconnected, resilient and capable of addressing complex cross-border scientific challenges.

As part of the bibliometric analysis referenced previously, a network analysis, which makes it possible to identify patterns of collaboration across organisations, countries, and disciplines, was undertaken to offer additional insight into how the funding has facilitated partnerships and knowledge exchange.

Specifically, a co authorship network analysis¹³ was undertaken (Figure 19) which shows a wide range of collaborating countries beyond those in which the funded beneficiaries were based.

Figure 19: Co-authorship network of M-ERA.NET 3 publications using countries as a unit of analysis. An interactive version of this network is available by clicking on this [link](#)

M-ERA.NET 3 project participants are collaborating globally, far beyond the countries in which they were based

¹³ This assessed geographic relatedness based on the number of jointly authored publications. Country assignment was based on the home institutions of authors at the time of publication.

This illustrates the **global reach** of the consortia and indicates potential for ongoing impact and collaboration beyond the funding period. This analysis also highlights several super-connector countries, shown as larger nodes in the network, notably Germany (cluster of key collaborator countries shown in a yellow / green colour), Poland (cluster of key collaborator countries shown in green), Portugal (part of the cluster with Germany), and Spain (key collaborator countries shown in pink).

Scientific Publications and Knowledge Dissemination

The project coordinators consistently emphasised that participation in M-ERA.NET 3 projects has generated **substantial scientific output**, with publications and conference contributions specifically highlighted. Many projects reported **publication numbers that exceeded their original expectations**, reflecting both the scientific excellence of the work undertaken and the productive, transnational collaboration enabled by M-ERA.NET 3 funding. Dissemination activities were typically broad, spanning peer-reviewed journal articles, conference presentations, invited talks, workshops, and, where appropriate, proceedings papers. Several coordinators highlighted that M-ERA.NET 3's scale and focus create **favourable conditions** for producing high-quality scientific outputs. The **consortia are small enough** to maintain deep technical engagement, yet international enough to generate novel insights, comparative datasets, and complementary expertise that strengthen the rigour and visibility of published results. As a result, dissemination activities often **extended beyond the project period**, with publications continuing to emerge as analyses were completed. In some cases, these outputs also served as a platform for further collaboration, enabling partners to secure **follow-on funding**, attract new research partners, and reinforce institutional research strategies.

As an additional measure of this output, the publications reported in the final reports of each M-ERA.NET funded project were further analysed, where data were available. As noted previously, 1,017 publications were identified and, as of 2025, these publications have received an average of 21 citations each, with an average journal impact factor of 5.86, indicating that much of the funded research has been published in reputable, high-impact journals, as shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Summary bibliometric data of M-ERA.NET publications – number of citations per publication and impact factors of the journals in which the articles were published

There are many influential, highly cited scientific papers produced through M-ERA.NET funded projects much of which has been published in reputable, high-impact journals

Patents and Intellectual Property

The creation and protection of intellectual property was highlighted as a **key output** of a number of M-ERA.NET 3 projects (as well as of some of the projects funded through earlier M-ERA.NET phases), often representing the first protectable results emerging from early-stage materials research.

The final reports of M-ERA.NET funded projects that were available (not just M-ERA.NET 3 funded projects as the majority of these are not yet completed and, therefore, there are no final reports) were reviewed, which identified 110 patent filings across 163 projects. The duration of the projects is 3 years, thus, it is almost safe to assume that project reports that are published in 2018, for example, originate from projects that were funded 3 years earlier, i.e. in 2015. However, there can be no assignment of the patents to the call years as projects might have been extended. Interestingly, though, notwithstanding the above considerations, based on the following figure, the calls in 2015 and 2017 that supported the lowest number of projects resulted in the highest number of patents three years later.

Figure 21: Number of funded projects by call year and number of reported patents three years later (as reported in M-ERA.NET project final reports, by year of final report publication)

A momentum seems to be growing after 2018. More than 20 patents per year are being filed since then.

Patents were filed on a **diverse range of innovations**, including catalyst synthesis methods, coating processes, nanomaterial formulations, biosensing technologies and device architectures. In several cases, patents were strategically prioritised before publications, with scientific papers deliberately delayed until IP protection was secured. This highlights an important feature of the programme: **although focused on low- to mid-TRL research, M-ERA.NET provides an environment where novel scientific insights can mature into innovations with clear commercial potential**. Beneficiaries noted that the **breadth of expertise** within transnational consortia often **accelerated invention**, enabling new combinations of materials, processes and testing capabilities that would have been difficult to achieve within national boundaries alone.

A number of projects demonstrated particularly strong **IP performance**. For example, one nanotechnology-oriented consortium generated two international patents (United States and Japan). Another project developing circular-economy catalysts for methane pyrolysis filed a national patent in Lithuania, protecting a newly developed synthesis route that connects waste-derived alumina catalyst supports with advanced plasma-assisted regeneration methods. In security materials research, partners prepared patent applications covering luminescent formulations and smartphone-based authentication systems, although dissemination was kept deliberately limited due to the sensitivity of the application domain. These examples illustrate how M-ERA.NET 3 enables early-stage concepts to progress rapidly toward protectable technological advances.

Beyond the patents themselves, many beneficiaries emphasised the **broader strategic value of IP generation**. Patents supported **future funding** applications, strengthened institutional **technology portfolios** and, in some cases, directly enabled **follow-on collaborations** with industry. They also contributed to internal **capacity building**, with several organisations reporting that M-ERA.NET projects helped them refine their IP management practices, build experience in transnational exploitation planning and engage more effectively with technology transfer offices. Although most projects remained at pre-commercial TRLs, the **volume and quality of intellectual property** emerging across the portfolio demonstrate that M-ERA.NET plays a meaningful role in **shaping Europe's innovation pipeline**, bridging fundamental materials research and applied technological development.

IMPACTS AND IMPACT PATHWAYS

This section summarises the expected **impact on policy, economy and society** (policy alignment/ influence, economy & innovation, scientific, networking, capacity building, less-engaged countries, value chains, internationalisation). Emerging **impact pathways** are also presented based on the interviews with coordinators of projects financed by M-ERA.NET 3.

SCIENTIFIC AND RESEARCH COMMUNITY IMPACTS

The strongest and most visible impacts of the projects are on research communities. M-ERA.NET 3 has created **critical mass, provided international visibility, and fostered durable consortia**. These impacts are amplified by the inclusiveness of topic setting, which ensures that a wide range of national priorities can find resonance in M-ERA.NET 3 calls, thus reinforcing researcher motivation and engagement.

Participation in M-ERA.NET 3 (and previous M-ERA.NET phases) funded projects has generated a wide range of scientific, technological, organisational and collaborative impacts for beneficiaries across Europe and beyond. Although projects differ in scale, technology domain, and maturity, a set of consistent impact themes have emerged.

Online survey respondents were asked to **rate the level of impact** they expect to achieve as a result of participating in M-ERA.NET 3 calls, across a range of scientific, commercial, and strategic dimensions. Overall, the results, as show in Figure 22, indicate strong expectations of positive impact, with most respondents selecting “moderate” or “high” for the majority of factors. Only a small proportion reported “low” or “no impact,” suggesting broad confidence in the long-term value of the programme.

Figure 22: Project impacts

Scientific and collaboration impacts are evident, while broader economic and societal impacts are still emerging

The **highest expected impacts** are concentrated in research-oriented and collaboration-driven areas, which aligns closely with M-ERA.NET 3's mission. In particular:

- Respondents reported very strong expectations of engagement in new research fields (164 high and 74 moderate)
- Enhanced knowledge base and skills (161 high and 86 moderate)
- Durable international collaborations (165 high and 63 moderate)
- New international collaboration opportunities (182 high and 57 moderate), and increased publications (132 high and 90 moderate)

Similarly, improvements in **reputation and network visibility** were widely anticipated (142 high and 88 moderate). These responses demonstrate that participants see the network as a powerful driver of scientific advancement, internationalisation, and long-term research cooperation.

Similar themes emerged in the interviews with project coordinators. Many highlighted the **capacity-building** effects within research teams, especially in terms of skills development, cross-disciplinary learning and exposure to new methodologies. **Interdisciplinary engagement** allowed researchers to gain experience outside their core science or technology domain, strengthening both individual competencies and the collective capability of their institutions. Several projects involved training of early-career researchers, supervision of theses, and integration of project results into teaching and laboratory practice, indicating a sustained spill-over into **academic development**.

Another widely cited impact was the **strengthening of scientific cohesion, trust and coordination** across institutions. Project leads described the collaboration as “*collegial, efficient and motivating*”, with many reporting that interactions were “*very rewarding and fruitful*” in terms of scientific exchange and shared problem-solving. This collegiality contributed to smoother project delivery, but also built **social capital** that partners intended to carry into future joint proposals. In several cases, teams had already submitted or secured follow-on proposals together, demonstrating the **durability** of these relationships.

A major theme was the creation of new, or strengthening of existing **international research networks**. Coordinators repeatedly described how participation in M-ERA.NET 3 (and previous phases) funded projects broadened their scientific communities, introduced new partners and opened new avenues for collaboration. Many stressed that **these partnerships would not have formed through national calls**, with one coordinator noting the value of “*access to complementary European expertise and test facilities,*” which materially expanded what their teams could achieve. International cooperation was also noted as being particularly important for smaller regions and countries with limited domestic infrastructure, with another interviewee stating that:

“collaboration opened perspectives not only in terms of work, but essentially in terms of expertise, know-how and collaboration—things that we cannot do actually on our side alone”.

Finally, M-ERA.NET 3 produced meaningful institutional impacts, including **strategic alignment** with organisational priorities, **increased visibility** for research groups, and **stronger positioning within European** research communities. Participation helped institutions refine their research agendas, expand access to international facilities, and engage more confidently in larger EU programmes. For many coordinators, the

programme also offered a **manageable, mid-scale format that encouraged experimentation** and scientific creativity, supporting new research directions that might not have been feasible under more rigid funding schemes.

Commercial and economic impacts show a more mixed pattern. While some respondents expect positive outcomes (including new commercial revenue, access to new markets, and commercial exploitation strategies) these categories display higher proportions of “low” or “no impact” responses compared with research-related impacts. **Commercialisation outcomes** are seen as more **uncertain or longer-term**, consistent with the mid-TRL nature of M-ERA.NET 3 projects and the maturity levels typical in advanced materials research.

Respondents were asked to indicate the targeted TRL of their M-ERA.NET 3 project. The distribution shows that respondents most commonly targeted mid-range TRLs, with the highest concentrations at TRL 4 and TRL 5. This pattern demonstrates a strong emphasis on applied research and early-stage development, which is typical for collaborative materials research programmes. This aligns well with **M-ERA.NET 3’s role in supporting transnational projects that bridge the gap between fundamental materials science and industrial application**, enabling technologies to advance from concept towards feasibility and proof-of-concept.

Respondents were asked to estimate the expected timeframe for commercialisation of results arising from their M-ERA.NET 3 project. A sizable portion of respondents indicated that commercialisation is expected within three to five years, suggesting that many projects are positioned at a stage where applied research outcomes could feasibly progress towards market readiness with further development work.

Figure 23: Target TRL

Figure 24: Time to market

M-ERA.NET 3 projects primarily progress technologies to mid-TRL stages, with commercialisation expected in the medium to long term

Respondents were asked to rate how the impacts achieved to date compare with the impacts they originally anticipated at the start of their M-ERA.NET 3 project, using a scale from 1 (much lower) to 5 (much higher). The distribution of responses shows that most participants reported impacts that were broadly in line with expectations (scored 3 in Figure 25: Impacts achieved vs anticipated)

A substantial number of respondents reported impacts that were higher than expected, with 72 respondents

selecting “4” and 33 respondents selecting “5”. This suggests that for many participants, the project delivered more positive impacts than initially anticipated, particularly in areas related to collaboration, scientific advancement, and capability development, as evidenced in earlier datasets. Only a small number of respondents (15) indicated that impacts were lower than anticipated (“2”), and only one respondent reported impacts that were “much lower” (“1”), suggesting that significant underperformance was rare among the projects surveyed.

Figure 25: Impacts achieved vs anticipated

Scientific and collaboration impacts are already being realised, while economic and societal impacts are largely anticipated for the coming years.

Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which their M-ERA.NET 3 projects had achieved, or were expected to achieve, a range of **wider impacts beyond the immediate scientific and technical outcomes**. The results show a clear differentiation between the types of wider impacts being generated, with particularly **strong contributions in scientific advancement and environmental sustainability**, and more modest impacts in areas directly linked to jobs, public health, and policy influence.

The strongest performance was observed in impacts related to scientific and technical advancement:

- “Advancement of related scientific or technical fields” received overwhelmingly positive ratings, with 173 respondents selecting ‘high’ and only a very small number reporting low or no impact.
- A similar pattern was seen in “advancement in the field of advanced materials,” which received 195 ‘high’ ratings, confirming that M-ERA.NET is making a significant contribution to Europe’s scientific leadership in advanced materials research.

Figure 26: Wider impacts

Projects contribute to wider scientific, societal and economic benefits, with many impacts expected to materialise over the longer term.

Advancements in the field of advanced materials and in related scientific and technology fields was also strongly emphasised by the project coordinators that were interviewed. M-ERA.NET 3 (and previous M-ERA.NET phases) funded projects have collectively delivered, or are aiming to deliver, a broad set of scientific and technological advances, driven by the integration of materials development, characterisation, modelling and application-focused testing across international teams. Many consortia **generated new or enhanced material systems**, including, for example, advanced metal alloys, 3D-printed photocatalytic structures, biocompatible materials, catalytic coatings, and functional nanomaterials for sensors and medical applications. These developments were frequently **underpinned by parallel developments in analytical and modelling tools**, with project coordinators reporting improvements in imaging techniques, oxidation and degradation testing, computational materials science, and electrochemical characterisation.

Technological development was also highlighted by a number of project coordinators. Several projects resulted in **advances in manufacturing methods** such as additive manufacturing of multi-material systems, laser surface texturing for biomedical devices, inkjet printing of energy-related materials, and the integration of disparate computational tools into open-innovation platforms. In some cases, these advances **translated into validated prototypes and demonstrators**, including catalyst-coated membranes tested under automotive conditions, biosensors based on enzymatic inks and nanomaterials, and high-performance coatings assessed through rigorous industrial testing. Many projects advanced from low TRLs to TRL 4–5, with one coordinator noting that they:

“...Started with disparate tools at low TRLs and the aim was, mainly, to develop a platform that is at TRL 4–5. At the end we succeeded to get this because the platform exists, the tools are integrated.”

Another area showing particularly strong expected impact is **contribution to environmental sustainability**, where 115 respondents rated the impact as ‘high’ and a further 95 as ‘moderate’. This aligns with the network’s thematic orientation toward materials innovation, energy transition, resource efficiency, and low-carbon technologies.

In contrast, **wider socio-economic impacts** (such as job creation, public health improvements, and policy or regulatory input) **exhibited more mixed responses**. While some respondents anticipate positive contributions, these categories include higher proportions of “low” and “no impact” ratings, indicating that such outcomes are either less central to the projects’ objectives or lie further downstream in the innovation pathway. For example, job creation had a balanced distribution (52 low, 107 moderate, 51 high), while **policy/regulatory impact showed the weakest performance**, with 78 respondents reporting “no impact”.

Overall, the pattern of responses, across a range of impact factors, **reinforces the programme’s core strengths: strengthening international networks, enhancing scientific capability, supporting entry into new research fields, and building durable collaboration pathways**. While commercial outcomes are expected by some, expectations are more variable, reflecting the early-stage of technology development in many projects. These findings underline the **importance of M-ERA.NET 3 as a mechanism for deepening research excellence and international engagement**, while also **highlighting opportunities to provide more structured pathways for commercialisation and market uptake** where appropriate.

INDUSTRIAL (INCL. SME) IMPACTS

In a similar vein, based on evidence from the online survey, interviews with project coordinators and network-level data, impacts for industry and SMEs are, mainly concentrated in **capability development, collaboration, and early-stage innovation** rather than immediate commercial outcomes, again reflecting the mid-TRL focus of the programme.

Across the online survey, respondents reported strong industrial-adjacent outcomes, particularly in areas linked to collaboration and applied research. A total of 125 respondents indicated **access to new international industry partners**, highlighting that M-ERA.NET 3 plays an important enabling role in forming cross-border partnerships that would not typically arise through national funding alone. Similarly, 100 respondents reported achieving **new or improved products, processes, or services**, indicating that applied technological development is occurring within many projects, even if commercialisation remains longer-term.

The network-level data show that SME involvement in M-ERA.NET 3 (and previous M-ERA.NET phases) is comparatively high relative to other ERA-NETs. SMEs account for approximately 23% of participants in M-ERA.NET 3 (with even higher percentages in earlier phases) and in some countries, such as Austria, Denmark and Sweden, one in two project partners is an SME or large company. While the limited level of industry engagement and the challenges facing SME participation are acknowledged, the network members emphasised that **M-ERA.NET 3’s manageable project size, moderate administrative burden, and mid-TRL**

orientation make it more attractive to companies than many Horizon Europe instruments.

The impacts for participating companies, particularly **SMEs**, appear most significant in relation to **knowledge acquisition, enhanced scientific capabilities and strengthened international visibility**. Survey respondents reported high expectations of impact in areas such as entering new research fields, accessing new know-how, and enhancing skills. These findings were reinforced by project coordinator interviews, where coordinators, reporting on behalf of SME, partners, highlighted that SMEs viewed participation in M-ERA.NET 3 funded projects as an **important mechanism for accessing specialised expertise and advanced research infrastructures that would otherwise be beyond reach**.

Commercial impacts, while achieved in some projects, are more variable. Survey data (in Figures 22 to 26) show that anticipated commercial revenue, market access and formal exploitation strategies receive more mixed scores. This, however, reflects the fact that most projects have achieved outputs that sit at TRL 4–5 where commercialisation pathways remain emergent. Nonetheless, the network has supported meaningful early-stage innovation. As has already been discussed, patent generation across the portfolio (110 filings identified in project final reports) and the development of protectable IP in several high-performing projects illustrate that **industrially relevant knowledge is being generated**. Interviews confirm that for some SMEs, securing IP or demonstrating proof-of-concept through M-ERA.NET 3 funding has directly supported subsequent investor discussions or follow-on funding applications.

M-ERA.NET 3 has also **contributed to industrial readiness and future market potential by maturing technologies to a point where they can move** into national funding programmes, Horizon Europe calls, or private R&D pipelines for further development. Time-to-market data from the survey indicate that many organisations expect commercial applications within 3–5 years, consistent with the mid-TRL positioning of the projects. Additionally, several project coordinators noted that collaboration with industrial partners influenced project direction and provided early insights on manufacturability, scaling, and regulatory considerations.

However, **barriers to fuller industrial engagement remain**. Interviews highlighted issues such as long call and contracting timelines, state-aid constraints, and limited proposal-writing capacity in SMEs. Some partners suggested separate scoring or ranking mechanisms (relative to academia led proposals) for industry-led proposals as well as stronger dissemination to mobilise industrial communities, recognising that visible success stories are often key to encouraging new SME participation.

Overall, the evidence indicates that **M-ERA.NET 3 is effective in engaging SMEs and companies, strengthening their research capabilities, and supporting early-stage technological innovation**, even if the achievement of downstream commercial impacts typically requires additional funding for further development. The programme's structure (international, mid-TRL, and thematically broad) positions it as an **important bridge between fundamental research and industrial deployment**, with clear added value for Europe's advanced materials sector.

EMERGING IMPACT PATHWAYS

From the above analysis, it is clear that a number of pathways to impact are emerging:

- **Further research and refinement of early scientific results** - many projects have produced promising results and findings that now require additional experimentation, extended dataset development or deeper mechanistic understanding to reach technical stability. Coordinators emphasised that core scientific questions remain and that progressing these results will require continued research effort beyond the initial funding period.
- **Strengthened industry engagement** to shape use cases and adoption pathways -in projects with industrial partners, they played an important role in defining requirements, validating early materials and informing design constraints. Coordinators without industrial partners stated that stronger engagement will be necessary to translate results into operational settings. For several projects, industry input directly influenced testing protocols and material specifications, demonstrating the importance of deeper collaboration as technologies evolve.
- **Regulatory, certification and standards alignment** - projects in the areas of biomedicine, recycling, coatings and energy systems stressed that regulatory and standards compliance will shape their path to impact. ISO biocompatibility requirements, environmental and safety regulations, and sector-specific certification (e.g., for industrial materials or medical-device components) were identified as essential next steps. As one coordinator commented, "*Certification and legislation... that's what the further work is now*" underscoring the centrality of regulatory alignment for deployment.
- **Prototype optimisation and industrial-environment testing** - although many consortia delivered functional prototypes, coordinators stressed that these must be refined and validated under real application conditions to determine durability, long-term behaviour and performance. Field testing or industrial trials will, therefore, be required to verify reliability beyond controlled laboratory environments.
- **Pilot manufacturing or process-integration trials** - the need to validate whether laboratory-scale processes can operate effectively within industrial production settings was highlighted. This includes assessing reproducibility, throughput and compatibility with existing equipment and processes. Pilot-scale trials were described as an essential bridge between scientific feasibility and operational viability.
- **Higher-TRL scale-up funding** - a recurring message was that follow-on investment is needed to move from mid-TRL demonstrators to commercially relevant maturity. Coordinators reported applying to Horizon Europe, national innovation programmes or EIC Pathfinder calls to support scale-up activities, recognising that M-ERA.NET 3 effectively seeds technology development but does not fund the later stages required for market readiness.
- **Intellectual property development to secure commercial potential** - multiple projects filed or prepared patents, recognising IP as central to protecting competitive advantage, structuring collaborations and attracting investment. Coordinators noted that IP frameworks provide the foundation for future exploitation, including licensing, spin-out activity or long-term industrial partnerships.

POLICY AND SYSTEMIC IMPACTS

At a policy level, M-ERA.NET 3 contributes to reducing fragmentation, as stated by its members, by **aligning national and regional programmes**. Its annual calls feed directly into domestic policies and roadmaps in countries and regions like Slovenia, Romania, Türkiye, Spain, and Saxony.

The perspectives of representatives of the European Commission DG RTD, consulted during this assessment, underscore the systemic impacts that have been achieved. M-ERA.NET 3 is **valued as a tool for policy coherence and alignment, reducing fragmentation of national strategies**. Its outputs, such as the [Materipedia](#) database, are recognised as assets that contribute beyond the projects themselves. Its **influence on high-level EU legislation, however, remains indirect**, although it was the view of R&I project coordinators that projects have made, or are making, meaningful contributions to, or were strongly aligned with, a wide range of EU policy priorities, even when this was not the primary driver of the research design. The strongest areas of alignment relate to EU strategies on climate neutrality, circular economy, clean energy, sustainable mobility, and advanced materials innovation. Several projects directly addressed themes within the European Green Deal, including reducing transport related emissions through lightweight materials, low-carbon production processes, and the development of technologies that support the net zero transition such as fuel-cell components, hydrogen materials, and photocatalytic reactors. Coordinators working on recycling-oriented or circular-materials projects highlighted contributions to EU ambitions on resource efficiency, waste reduction and critical-raw-materials recovery, with one noting explicit alignment with circular-economy and sustainability goals.

INSTITUTIONAL AND GOVERNANCE IMPACTS

A key, and often underappreciated, layer of impact concerns the network members themselves. **Institutional impacts are another strong dimension**. Participation in M-ERA.NET 3 (and earlier phases) has driven internal reforms, improved capacities, and modernised procedures in multiple agencies. As examples:

- **Romania** aligned its monitoring systems with international standards, reinforcing credibility.
- **Slovenia** built up its ability to manage international R&I programmes despite historically being a policy ministry and described how participation required building a compatible national system for transnational funding, a challenging but ultimately positive institutional reform.
- **Latvia** created a unit dedicated to international networks.
- **France, Spain, and Portugal** all pointed to the value of M-ERA.NET's shared procedures, particularly the centralised evaluation process, which not only improved the fairness and credibility of calls but also provided models that could inform national practice and were replicated in other networks.
- **Germany** noted that internal coherence improved thanks to cross-departmental collaboration between national and European teams, which was fostered by M-ERA.NET participation.
- **Taiwan** reinforced its advisory structures by appointing experts to guide participation.
- For **Türkiye**, M-ERA.NET was a laboratory for importing "*international best practices*," from evaluation procedures to peer learning.

The participating **regions** also highlighted important institutional impacts.

- **Flanders/VLAIO (Belgium)** integrated M-ERA.NET into existing roles and adjusted its national incentives.
- **Saxony (Germany)** established a dedicated programme in advanced materials to facilitate funding of projects under M-ERA.NET and deepened inter-ministerial cooperation to facilitate support of a wider TRL span.
- **The São Paulo region in Brazil** adopted European best practices on open science and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), using internationalisation as leverage for domestic change.
- **Asturias (Spain)**, despite limited success in terms of funded projects, reported major institutional impacts, including exposure to European evaluation methodologies and concepts like Technology Readiness Levels and Responsible Research and Innovation, influenced its internal policy thinking.

This illustrates how M-ERA.NET, across all phases, has **strengthened institutional capacity and resilience**, even if participation levels vary. At the same time, there is wide consensus among partners that the exchange with peers across countries enabled by the network has been valuable. Smaller or newer agencies reported that exposure to established practices helped them modernise their operations. Experienced funders also benefited from exposure to different national contexts. Slovenia highlighted the value of structured RRI guidelines developed within M-ERA.NET 3, which could then be applied nationally beyond the network. Brazil and Taiwan emphasised that M-ERA.NET participation helped them align with European standards, particularly on open science, RRI, and evaluation methodologies. Overall, it is safe to state that M-ERA.NET (all phases) has functioned as a “school” for governance, helping its members improve and align with international norms.

ADDED VALUE/ ADDITIONALITY

This section addresses additionality and added-value as follows:

- Additionality in relation to the **leverage effect** in terms of the level to which the EU funding attracts additional public funding at national/regional level.
- Additionality in terms of **performance and outputs** of M-ERA.NET 3 **compared to other networks** and initiatives.
- European added value: what is the additional value resulting from the network, **compared to what could be achieved by Member States alone** at national and/or regional levels.
- Behavioural additionality in terms of **changes in behavioural of participants** in the projects funded by the network.
- Additionality in terms of what happened to the project ideas that did not get the requested funding (**counterfactual dimension**).

LEVERAGE EFFECT

The leverage effect regarding the two co-funded calls, 2016 and 2021, defined as the actual funding to calls by partners divided by EU top-up) is significantly higher compared to the leverage of European Partnerships (BMR 2024). Although there is a lack of data for co-funded partnerships at the time of writing the BMR 2024, M-ERA.NET 3 presents a much higher leverage than all the other partnerships.

Table 6: Call leverage of EU co-funded calls in M-ERA.NET and in Horizon Europe European Partnerships

M-ERA.NET 3	Call 2021	M-ERA.NET 2	Call 2016
Call leverage	5.35	Call leverage	2.58
Partners' contributions	€ 58,901,973	Partners' contributions	€ 23,263,438
EU top-up funding received	€ 11,002,643	EU top-up funding received	€ 8,995,362

Source: FFG data

European Partnerships	Call leverage
Co-funded	No data
Co-programmed	0.14
Institutionalised (Art 185/187)	0.88
KICs	0.59

Source: BMR 2024

M-ERA.NET presents significantly higher leverage effect than European Partnerships under Horizon Europe

ADDITIONALITY WHEN COMPARED TO OTHER NETWORKS/ PROGRAMMES

Online survey respondents were asked to compare their experience of M-ERA.NET 3 with other international funding programmes across a series of dimensions. The results, presented in Figure 27, show that a clear majority of respondents rated M-ERA.NET 3 as “better” or “the same” as comparable programmes across all factors.

Figure 27: Comparison with other networks

M-ERA.NET 3 is viewed as comparable to, and in some aspects more accessible than, other transnational research funding programmes.

- M-ERA.NET 3 performs particularly strongly in areas related to collaboration and project structure. High proportions of respondents rated the programme as better in terms of offering **manageable project sizes that support effective collaboration, the attractiveness of the programme to newcomers, and the speed and flexibility of implementation.**
- Other dimensions where respondents identified M-ERA.NET 3 as comparatively strong include **lowering administrative burden, accessing high-quality expertise and facilities, and achieving ambitious research outcomes.** In these areas, the number of “better” ratings is consistently higher than the number of “worse” ratings, often by a significant margin.

Areas where **perceptions were more balanced include coverage of the whole value chain, exploitation of research results, and effective project management.** While these factors still received a strong proportion of “better” and “same” responses, they also show slightly higher levels of “worse” ratings compared with other categories, suggesting mixed experiences among participants. A much smaller proportion selected “worse,” and a consistent subset indicated “not applicable,” reflecting those for whom this was their first international project.

The interviews with the members of the network also highlighted that **M-ERA.NET 3 is unusual for its thematic breadth.** Whereas ERA-MIN focuses narrowly on raw materials, or QuantERA on quantum, M-ERA.NET 3 covers the **full span of advanced materials research**, from nanotechnology to energy applications to circular economy. This breadth allows smaller countries and regions to find niches where their research priorities align, without being excluded by overly rigid agendas. Portugal, Slovenia, and Latvia highlighted this as a unique strength: in more narrowly defined ERA-NETs, their participation options were limited, but M-ERA.NET 3’s broad calls gave them room to engage. Non-European partners like Taiwan and Brazil confirmed that this breadth made it worthwhile for them to participate, since their own national strategies span multiple material domains.

EUROPEAN ADDED VALUE OF M-ERA.NET 3

M-ERA.NET 3 generates a level of added value that national or regional programmes cannot reproduce on their own, because it **creates a transnational research environment that expands the scale, diversity, and quality of collaboration far beyond what any Member State could achieve independently.** The interviews with the network members show, repeatedly, that countries join the network precisely because their domestic systems cannot cover the full breadth of advanced materials research or mobilise comparable critical mass of financial resources but also research capacity especially in smaller countries. Smaller research communities and/or newer member States such as Latvia, Slovenia, Portugal, or Romania describe M-ERA.NET 3 as essential for overcoming structural limitations, since national budgets, thematic coverage, and community size would not allow their researchers to participate in ambitious international collaborations without this framework. Larger countries like Germany and Spain also emphasise how the network enables them to embed their strong research communities into global circuits of knowledge production, something no national call can replicate.

At a **regional level**, actors such as Saxony and Asturias underline that M-ERA.NET 3 gives them an internationalisation pathway that regional programmes alone could never provide. The network’s structured, jointly run evaluation processes, its inclusive topic-setting approach, and its capacity to integrate partners from Europe and beyond create a shared scientific and policy space that national schemes cannot generate on their own. This shared space strengthens alignment of priorities, reduces fragmentation, and produces collaboration patterns that are qualitatively different from bilateral or domestic initiatives.

In summary, the additional value of M-ERA.NET 3 arises from its ability to create an integrated, international ecosystem in advanced materials research, enabling critical mass, alignment, institutional learning, and global reach that no Member State or region could generate acting alone.

BEHAVIOURAL ADDITIONALITY

Behavioural additionality was addressed in the online survey completed by project applicants. Survey respondents were asked to indicate whether participation in their M-ERA.NET 3 project had led to specific **organisational changes or behaviours**. The results show a strong pattern of positive organisational effects, particularly in areas related to partnership development and engagement with international funding opportunities. The most prominent change reported was the **formation of new R&I consortia**, with 155 respondents selecting “Yes” and a further 74 selecting “Partially.” Only 24 respondents reported no such change, indicating that encouraging and enabling collaboration is one of the most widespread outcomes of participation. A similarly strong positive response was observed for **participation in other EU or international funding calls**, where 123 respondents reported “Yes” and 85 “Partially,” suggesting that involvement in M-ERA.NET 3 often acts as a springboard to further international R&D activity.

Figure 28: Organisational or behavioural change

Participation in M-ERA.NET influences beneficiaries’ collaboration behaviour, encouraging new partnerships and future international engagement.

Other organisational changes were more mixed but still show notable positive influence. **Engagement with end-users was enhanced** for many participants (51 Yes, 105 Partially), and the **development of sustainability or RRI strategies** was also affected to some extent (47 Yes, 115 Partially).

Survey results indicate that M-ERA.NET 3 projects are also contributing to behavioural additionality through the integration of cross-cutting RRI dimensions. Environmental relevance and open science/data protection were the most strongly addressed factors, with the majority of respondents rating these aspects highly (scores of 4 or 5). Gender equality, ethics, stakeholder engagement and societal relevance show a more mixed distribution of responses, suggesting that while these aspects are being considered across many projects, their level of integration varies depending on project focus and maturity.

Responses regarding the usefulness of the RRI guidelines further support this interpretation. Most respondents rated the guidelines as moderately to very helpful, with the largest share selecting the midpoint rating and a substantial number reporting that the guidance was helpful or very helpful. This suggests that RRI considerations are becoming embedded within project design and implementation, even where they do not directly influence the focus or direction of the research.

Figure 29: Behavioural change – cross cutting factors

M-ERA.NET projects increasingly integrate environmental, open science and wider RRI considerations into their research activities

Project beneficiaries were also asked about RRI during interviews. There was no indication that RRI had any significant influence on either proposal preparation or project delivery. From a proposal preparation perspective, many of the beneficiaries noted that they already had experience of the requirements of RRI through the preparation of proposals for other funding mechanisms. If it was the first time that the beneficiary had led proposal preparation, they sought advice, as required, from support functions in their

institutions (all project beneficiaries interviewed came from universities or research organisation).

Considering project delivery, many of the beneficiaries interviewed indicated that RRI, again, did not have any significant influence. It was highlighted, however, that the scientific topics covered and activities undertaken naturally aligned with the requirements of RRI, specifically from an environmental and sustainability perspective. This was to be expected since the call topics covered areas such energy materials, batteries and, more recently, clean energy technologies, circular economy, etc.

Together, these findings indicate that participation in M-ERA.NET 3 encourages researchers and organisations to integrate broader societal, environmental and open science considerations into their research activities, reinforcing behavioural change beyond purely scientific and technological outcomes.

Changes in R&D strategy show the most limited impact among the items assessed. Only 28 respondents reported that their organisation had changed its R&D strategy as a result of participation, while 84 reported partial change and 141 reported no change. This indicates that while **M-ERA.NET 3 can influence operational behaviours such as collaborations or engagement patterns, it is less likely to directly reshape high-level organisational strategy**. Similarly, changes in views on transnational collaboration were modestly positive (69 Yes, 96 Partially, 88 No), suggesting that the programme reinforces existing positive perceptions rather than transforming organisational attitudes.

Overall, the results demonstrate that M-ERA.NET 3 has a **strong and consistent effect** on building new partnerships, widening participation in international funding, and progressively **strengthening organisational practices related to collaboration, sustainability, and external engagement**. The more limited influence on core R&D strategy is not unexpected, as such changes typically require sustained engagement over multiple projects or funding cycles. These findings highlight the network's value, not only in delivering research outcomes, but also in shaping organisational behaviour in ways that support long-term internationalisation and strategic capability development.

“All these projects have led me to participate in consortia that submitted proposals to various European competitions, even if not all of them were successful. The experience gained through these initiatives has helped me to improve my proposal writing skills and to structure and present my research in a clearer and more visible manner.”

ADDITIONALITY - THE COUNTERFACTUAL DIMENSION

Respondents whose projects were not funded were asked whether participation in the application process nevertheless brought any benefits. The results indicate that, for many applicants, **engagement with M-ERA.NET 3 (and earlier phases) generated positive outcomes despite an unsuccessful funding decision**. The most frequently cited benefit was the development of new collaborations, reported by 110 respondents, highlighting the value of the application process itself as a mechanism for networking and partnership building. A further 92 respondents reported an improved understanding of the application process, suggesting that participation helped strengthen future proposal readiness. Additionally, 68 respondents gained insights into future R&D priorities, indicating learning benefits in terms of strategic direction and thematic alignment.

However, a **substantial number of respondents** (79 in total) reported that they **derived no benefit from the process**. This indicates that while many applicants experience indirect or developmental gains from participation, a sizeable minority do not perceive any added value beyond the funding outcome itself. A small number of respondents (13) selected “Other,” pointing to a limited range of additional, unclassified benefits.

Figure 30: Benefits despite an unsuccessful application

Even unsuccessful applicants report benefits, particularly new collaborations, learning and improved readiness for future funding

Overall, the results suggest that the M-ERA.NET application process (across all phases) delivers meaningful non-financial benefits for a significant proportion of unsuccessful applicants, particularly in the areas of collaboration building, learning, and strategic insight. This highlights the network’s broader value as a network-building and capability-development mechanism, even where projects are not funded. At the same time, the relatively high number of applicants reporting no benefit indicates potential scope to enhance transparency, learning feedback, and developmental support embedded within the application process, to help ensure that a greater proportion of participants derive value from their engagement regardless of outcome.

In addition, respondents whose **project ideas were not selected for funding** under M-ERA.NET 3 (and earlier phases) were asked what subsequently happened to those ideas. The results show a wide range of responses, with many applicants still in a period of uncertainty or further development. The most common outcome was that no decision had yet been taken on what to do with the project idea, reported by 125 respondents, indicating that for a **significant proportion of applicants the future of their proposed work remains undecided**.

A sizeable number of respondents reported that they had abandoned the specific project idea altogether (62 respondents), suggesting that **for some applicants the lack of M-ERA.NET funding represented a decisive barrier to progression**. At the same time, evidence of onward **progression through alternative routes is also**

apparent. 33 respondents reported that they had applied to another funding programme and were still awaiting a decision, while 19 respondents secured funding under a national programme call and 10 respondents obtained support through another international funding programme. A further 28 respondents selected “Other,” indicating a range of additional outcomes not captured by the predefined categories.

Figure 31: Unsuccessful applicants- next steps

Unsuccessful applicants remain engaged and plan to reapply in future calls.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that while a proportion of unsuccessful M-ERA.NET applications do progress through alternative funding routes, a substantial share of project ideas either remain in a state of uncertainty or are ultimately discontinued. **This highlights both the gateway role that M-ERA.NET can play in stimulating onward funding activity, and the fragility of many early-stage project ideas that rely heavily on a single funding opportunity to proceed.** The relatively high proportion of abandoned or undecided projects also suggests potential value in stronger signposting to alternative funding routes, follow-on support mechanisms, or advisory services to help applicants sustain momentum after an unsuccessful outcome.

STRATEGIC POSITIONING AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

This section summarises the findings from interviews with M-ERA.NET 3 network members, project beneficiaries and the **strategy workshop discussions**¹⁴ about the role of M-ERA.NET in the EU policy

¹⁴ A half-day, online workshop was organised in Dec 2025 to present the results of the assessment to date and, considering these results within the context of developments in the wider partnerships landscape and other relevant initiatives, to discuss the added value of M-ERA.NET, the potential growth prospects and future of the network. The event was attended by around 40 participants including M-ERA.NET 3 members and EC (DG RTD and HADEA) officials. A separate report presents the results of the discussions in more detail.

landscape in advanced materials and the future envisaged for the network.

All members of the consortium **agree that M-ERA.NET is indispensable**. For large states it projects influence and for smaller ones it ensures visibility. For third countries it offers the only structured pathway into European collaboration. For many agencies, the network's strategic value lies in its ability to fill a gap left by other European instruments. Horizon Europe supports large, high-TRL projects with complex consortia, but offers fewer opportunities for smaller, riskier, or mid-TRL research. National programmes, by contrast, often lack a strong transnational dimension. M-ERA.NET has positioned itself in this intermediate space: providing opportunities for small and medium-sized projects, encouraging risk-taking and experimentation, and fostering international collaboration that might not otherwise happen.

DG RTD explicitly recognised the network as **“instrumental” in reducing fragmentation and harmonising national strategies in advanced materials**. Tools like the [Materipedia database](#) and structured inputs to the Advanced Materials Technology Council demonstrate how M-ERA.NET contributes to European-level coordination. However, such contributions have been less visible and the network continues to lack strong political anchoring: operational excellence has not translated into formal recognition or influence comparable to sector-specific partnerships such as ERA-MIN. Despite its operational excellence, known by all stakeholders involved, M-ERA.NET 3 was not elevated to a co-funded partnership in Horizon Europe. This was perceived as a failure of recognition rather than performance.

One of the strongest messages from members is the **need to strengthen M-ERA.NET's strategic anchoring within European policy**. Many members pointed to the [“Advanced Materials for Industrial Leadership”](#) communication as a potential vehicle for re-establishing that visibility and hoped that the M-ERA.NET 4 follow-on network could align itself closely with it.

DG RTD itself acknowledged that M-ERA.NET provides valuable alignment and that it is complementary to other partnerships, such as IAM4EU, which has objectives that are very similar to those of M-ERA.NET. At the same time, with the upcoming European Digital Infrastructure (starting in 2026), it is important that new projects / partnerships connect to this to benefit from common datasets, shared tools and accessible platforms for all researchers. M-ERA.NET can also help to make this infrastructure both useful to and used by researchers. **Overall, the role of M-ERA.NET as a coordination and alignment mechanism among Member States remains central for reducing fragmentation, an EC signal that the network's connective function is increasingly recognised at policy level even as the precise operational form in FP10 remains open.**

The **strategy workshop** provided important insights regarding the role of M-ERA.NET in the EU policy landscape and some key aspects that can formulate the legacy of the network for the future, i.e. internationalisation, connections to the national and regional eco-systems, infrastructures and impact/valorisation.

A key message was that M-ERA.NET is **positioned as a timely connector in an EU landscape** where advanced materials are central to technological sovereignty, the clean transition and economic security. Its **added value lies in creating critical mass and coordination** that national efforts alone cannot achieve,

especially helping smaller or less research-intensive countries access resources, **build trust and integrate into the European Research Area**. This strategic elevation is expected to be reinforced through the forthcoming Advanced Materials Act and a stronger positioning of materials in the next Framework Programme alongside the European Competitiveness Fund and EIC support for disruptive and dual use technologies.

Participants reframed **open strategic autonomy in terms of collective resilience, linking research, raw materials and industrial application**, but **more effective bridging of the developmental “valley of death” (progressing from the laboratory to demonstration) was needed** to retain value and intellectual capital in Europe. **Internationalisation** was treated as necessary but as something that must be **selective and strategically aligned** rather than expansive for its own sake, because global collaboration is now entangled with geopolitical concerns about sovereignty and dual use knowledge. The workshop suggested that deeper partnerships should be pursued with countries whose research maturity and institutional reliability reinforce European priorities, with examples being Canada, Korea, Japan, the United States and selected Latin American partners, while cooperation with China was described as sensitive and divisive. At the same time, **confidence remained high in M-ERA.NET’s pragmatic, low bureaucracy model as a gateway** for international partners and as a complement to Horizon Europe, provided that expansion is incremental and anchored in trust, mutual benefit and existing relationships, supported by capacity building through mobility, training and gradual integration of less experienced partners. **The message was that internationalisation should prioritise depth over breadth so that M-ERA.NET strengthens its role as a value-based connector rather than diluting governance and focus through uncontrolled growth.**

A central part of the workshop focused on strengthening **connections to national and regional ecosystems**, especially by improving SME involvement and the continuity between funded projects and innovation infrastructures. As well as the structural, cultural and procedural barriers, and constraints created by national and regional eligibility rules, many SMEs either do not know about M-ERA.NET opportunities or see them as too complex and slow compared to familiar national schemes. Examples like Poland show that more **balanced cooperation is possible** when incentives are shaped accordingly. The most tangible gap was identified as the **absence of strong post project valorisation pathways**. **Proposed remedies** included technology transfer schemes linked to M-ERA.NET outputs, brokerage and matchmaking events for cross project collaboration, stronger partner finding and targeted information actions, and call design refinements such as rotating thematic priorities or separating rankings for academic and industry led projects, while keeping **M-ERA.NET fundamentally research driven but more intentionally connected to commercialisation routes**.

The impact and valorisation discussion deepened this logic by focusing on how a **mid TRL niche** can deliver clearer and more traceable benefits without sacrificing the **exploratory and risk taking characteristics that make it valuable**. A key bottleneck was identified in **limited researcher familiarity with impact pathways, IPR management and industry collaboration**. Suggestions again centred on targeted training and mentoring, clearer IPR guidance across multinational consortia, better signposting toward national schemes and Horizon Europe instruments that support later stages, light touch monitoring at three and five years post-project to capture delayed outcomes and improve future call design, and more systematic matchmaking between completed projects and industrial partners or investors.

Finally, participants noted that Europe possesses substantial **research and innovation infrastructure**, yet accessibility remains limited. The landscape of laboratories, test beds, pilot lines, and scale-up facilities is fragmented, often insufficiently visible, difficult to navigate, and characterised by uneven access shaped by institutional boundaries. Participants argued that M-ERA.NET could **increase its value by mapping facilities and equipment, systematically recording relevant information on capability and performance and embedding expectations** about shared use, standards and cross border access into call texts. The way forward, they concluded, centres around identifying and connecting what already exists, improving signposting and access pathways, promoting standardisation and interoperability, and aligning with initiatives such as the Innovative Advanced Materials Initiative. In addition, M-ERA.NET can play an important role as the interface between Member States and certain upcoming projects trying to create a federated digital infrastructure in Europe.

The overall conclusion was that besides the need for stronger political anchorage, M-ERA.NET's future legacy can be strengthened through pragmatic, strategic adjustments that deepen selective internationalisation, improve SME integration and post project continuity, strengthen impact planning and IPR clarity, and make infrastructures more visible and interoperable, so that the network's mid TRL research excellence translates more reliably into lasting value for European society and the economy.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

OVERALL ASSESSMENT AND PATHS FOR IMPROVEMENT

The evaluation of M-ERA.NET 3 (and, where appropriate earlier phases) highlighted that it **has evolved into a mature, stable, and well-functioning network for transnational cooperation in materials research, with strong governance and wide geographical coverage**. Nonetheless, to sustain and enhance its performance, several management-related **improvements were recommended**. These include simplifying and harmonising administrative procedures across national agencies and shortening the time between proposal submission and project start, as far as possible, as well as enhancing longer-term monitoring of project outcomes. Greater effectiveness around evaluation feedback, and the introduction of structured impact-tracking mechanisms was also advised to better capture long-term scientific, economic, and societal effects.

Regarding calls and dissemination, participants stressed the **importance of maintaining M-ERA.NET 3's flexible and inclusive approach while improving clarity and focus on topic formulation**. Broad thematic calls remain valuable for encouraging innovative, cross-disciplinary proposals, however, some prioritisation could help reduce over-subscription and facilitate strategic alignment with EU policy goals, including the Green Deal and the forthcoming Advanced Materials Act. **Enhanced dissemination** of success stories and project results through coordinated communication channels, targeted campaigns would strengthen visibility and participation of less active stakeholders (e.g. large companies and SMEs). National information days and better guidance for applicants were seen as effective ways to reach under-represented actors and smaller research communities.

On large company and SME engagement, the network was urged to **deepen cooperation between academia and business** by incentivising the participation of industrial partners and creating bridges to national or European innovation programs. Encouraging industrial leadership in selected calls and developing matchmaking mechanisms between completed projects and potential commercial partners were identified as promising steps.

In terms of efficiency, effectiveness and European added value, **M-ERA.NET 3 continues to demonstrate clear additionality** by leveraging national funds for collective goals, reducing fragmentation, and fostering learning among agencies. The network's collaborative culture, specifically its "health and connectivity", was praised, though maintaining active engagement of all partners will require continued support for capacity building and inclusivity. Overall, **M-ERA.NET's greatest potential lies in balancing its exploratory, high-risk scientific character with clearer impact pathways and behavioural additionality, nurturing a culture of collaboration, openness to industry, and strategic alignment with Europe's broader innovation ecosystem**.

Accordingly, the assessment of the level of achievement of the M-ERA.NET 3 objectives can be illustrated as follows.

Figure 32: Level of achievement of M-ERA.NET 3 goals.

To identify the reasons why the performance of M-ERA.NET 3 in some areas was less successful than in others, the assumptions underlying the intervention logic are revisited (cf. Table). In particular, the level of participation of some regions in the calls was moderate, while others faced challenges in relation to lack of harmonised rules across different funding sources and programme requirements. The diversity of sometimes incompatible rules and timings also remains a hurdle at the national level as highlighted in the interviews with both M-ERA.NET 3 members and project beneficiaries. Moreover, the 'limited resources' noted in some countries clearly explains the reluctance of these countries to be more engaged as well as their intermittent participation in calls. These assumptions can explain the moderate level of participation of some regions and achievement of the 'convergence of the national/ regional programmes'.

The 'support provided for the exploitation of results' seems to be less adequate and not covering what is needed for project outputs and technology developments to proceed on the innovation journey as noted by the members' interviews. At the same time, 'access to the additional expertise' is not evident (market, legal expertise, etc.). While researchers and companies are brought together early in the process, industry mobilisation is less than desired and SMEs also face challenges in making the most of their participation, as noted in the project interviews. Businesses may also lack 'internal abilities to capitalise on the knowledge created'. These assumptions may explain the low achievement in the 'exploitation of the results, and the moderate achievement in relation to 'collaboration between research and industry', or the enhancement of industrial capabilities and thus 'strengthening of the European tech leadership'.

Regarding the **engagement of industry and SMEs and the exploitation of the results**, a number of recommendations were made by both members of the consortium as well as project beneficiaries, including

- **Structured post-project monitoring** - introduce light-touch follow-up at 3 and 5 years to capture delayed outcomes such as patents, spin-offs, and industrial uptake. These insights could then be used to refine future call design and demonstrate long-term impact.
- **Enhanced dissemination and visibility** - develop a curated “success stories” pipeline targeting industry, policymakers, and investors and organise thematic webinars, policy briefings, and showcase events to amplify project results beyond academic circles.
- **Technology transfer and brokerage** - Create a ‘matchmaking’ platform linking completed projects with industrial partners, investors, and national innovation programmes and facilitate brokerage events and cross-project collaboration to accelerate commercialisation.
- **Impact planning** - strengthen the “impact plan” section in proposals with clearer guidance on valorisation, IP management, and exploitation strategies.
- **Integration with national and EU ecosystems** - signpost projects to Horizon Europe instruments, EIC Pathfinder, and national scale-up programmes for higher-TRL development.
- **Industrial engagement** - incentivise SME and industry participation where possible through dedicated call tracks or mandatory industrial involvement in selected topics.
- **Adoption pathways** - promote early engagement of end-users to validate prototypes and inform design requirements.
- **Cross-cutting impact pathways** – design calls to foster interdisciplinary consortia to address complex challenges and broaden application potential.

THE POTENTIAL POSITIVE IMPACTS OF A CONTINUED AND ENHANCED FUTURE M-ERA.NET

Regarding a future network in FP10, the evidence strongly suggests that a **continued and strengthened next phase would amplify a set of impacts that are already clearly emerging from the operation of M-ERA.NET 3**. The assessment shows that the network has evolved into one of the most trusted, best coordinated and most internationally connected instruments in the advanced materials landscape, and this strong foundation offers fertile ground for deeper and broader influence. The future network would likely expand the mobilisation of Europe’s research and innovation communities even further, since M-ERA.NET 3 already demonstrates a steady rise in applications, participant diversity and total funding commitments. Its ability to engage countries across the EU13, EU14 and beyond Europe reveals a rare capacity to reduce fragmentation while widening participation, and it can, therefore, intensify its contribution to a more cohesive and inclusive European Research Area. The credibility and responsiveness of its governance structures, repeatedly emphasised by both project beneficiaries and funders, would allow the future network to **act as a more visible and strategic coordination mechanism for advanced materials within Horizon Europe’s broader mission of technological sovereignty**.

One of the most notable impacts expected from a future M-ERA.NET lies in its support for scientific excellence and interdisciplinarity. M-ERA.NET 3 has already produced over a thousand publications, high citation rates and substantial patent activity, much of it emerging from small but highly effective consortia

that integrate chemistry, engineering, nanotechnology and biological sciences in ways that strengthen Europe's scientific leadership in advanced materials. A next phase would deepen these dynamics by reinforcing durable international collaborations, expanding thematic flexibility and continuing to seed early-stage breakthroughs that can mature along clearer impact pathways. These pathways, already identified in the assessment, include further refinement of promising scientific findings, pilot manufacturing trials, prototype optimisation and preparation for regulatory or standards alignment. The future M-ERA.NET would therefore consolidate a pipeline of mid-TRL innovation with clearer trajectories toward industrial adoption and market relevance.

Industry and SME impacts, although variable in their immediacy, show strong potential for growth under a reinforced M-ERA.NET. The evidence from M-ERA.NET 3 suggests that SMEs gain significantly in capability development, from access to specialised know-how and by participation in transnational innovation ecosystems. With enhanced coordination, stronger dissemination and more structured interaction with industrial stakeholders, the future network could improve technology uptake and accelerate the maturation of promising materials solutions.

The high leverage effect identified for M-ERA.NET 3, far exceeding those of other partnerships, indicates that even modest European co-funding can generate substantial national investment and robust participation. An equally strong and more visible network could, therefore, become a key driver for aligning national materials strategies, stimulating private investment and strengthening Europe's competitiveness in advanced manufacturing, clean technologies and circular-economy materials.

At systemic level, the assessment highlights that M-ERA.NET 3 is already used by many countries and regions as an instrument for policy alignment, strategic programming and long-term cooperation. Participants describe it as a space where critical mass is created, where national agendas can be coordinated and where emerging priorities in materials science can be translated into common action. A continued M-ERA.NET could formalise this role more powerfully by acting as a stable interface between national ministries, regional innovation agencies and EU-level strategic bodies.

Moreover, its current global reach along with the suggested strategic, controlled and selective approach for internationalisation will further enhance Europe's role in shaping international standards, maintaining scientific diplomacy and securing more resilient value chains, which are critical in the context of the European Green Deal and the accelerating demand for advanced materials in clean energy, mobility and digital technologies.

APPENDIX A: ONLINE SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR SUCCESSFUL AND UNSUCCESSFUL APPLICANTS

GENERAL INFORMATION

- Name of Respondent
- Email Address
- Name of Organisation
- Country: [Dropdown]
- Organisation Type: Higher Education, RTO, SME, Large Enterprise, Public Authority, or Other

EXPERIENCE IN M-ERA.NET

- Please indicate your level of experience in participating in international research funding programmes (1 = No experience, 5 = Extensive experience)
- How many M-ERA.NET funded projects have you been involved in?
- Please name the project(s)
- List projects in this format: Project 1, Project 2, Project 3, etc. Use this same format consistently in all questions that refer to project(s)
- Please specify your role in the project(s): Coordinator, Partner, N/A
 - Are any of these successor / follow-on to a previous project?
 - If yes, please provide name(s)

MOTIVATION TO PARTICIPATE

- To what extent did the following motivate your participation in the M-ERA.NET funded project? (from (1) not at all to (5) a very high extent)
 - Access to public funding
 - Access to international expertise/facilities
 - Build new relationships
 - Strengthen existing collaborations
 - Expand network of collaborations
 - Increase international profile
 - Position for future EU funding
 - Explore new R&D/innovation areas
 - Respond to all topics of strategic national priority
 - Learn from peers across Europe
- Other, please specify
- What was the approximate funding received by your organisation in this project?
 - < €100k
 - €100k-€250k
 - €250k-€500k
 - > €500k

ADDED VALUE OF TRANSNATIONAL COLLABORATION

- Compared to other international funding programmes, how do you rate (better, same, worse N/A (This is my first international project)) the M-ERA.NET in terms of:
 - Access to higher-quality expertise/facilities
 - Achieving more ambitious research outcomes
 - Producing better research outcomes
 - Covering the whole value chain
 - Managing the project effectively
 - Lowering administrative burden
 - Speed and flexibility in implementation
 - Manageable project size facilitating true collaboration
 - Level of interdisciplinarity of the research approach
 - Attractiveness to newcomers
 - Exploitation of research results
- Further comments?

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

- Which of the following outcomes have been achieved (yes, partially, no, N/A) as a result of your involvement in this international funding programme (consider only those that apply)?
 - Access to new know-how
 - Access to new international industry partners
 - Access to new international research institutions/universities
 - Long-term recruitment of staff
 - New scientific methods or data
 - New or improved product/service/process
 - Patent/licenses filed or approved
 - Peer-reviewed joint publications
 - Publications for non-academic audiences
 - Completed Master or PhD dissertations
 - Presentation to stakeholders or policy audiences
 - Contribution to standardisation/regulatory change
 - Creation of a spin-out company/new start-up
- Other, please specify
- What was the targeted Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the project(s)?
- What Technology Readiness Level (TRL) was achieved for the project(s)?
- If the TRL was not achieved, why?
- What is the timeframe for commercialisation of results from the project(s) (years to market)?
- Did the project(s) continue under a subsequent funding scheme? (e.g. Horizon Europe)

IMPACTS ON YOUR ORGANISATION

- Please rate the impacts you expect to achieve because of your involvement in this international funding programme: (low, moderate, high, no impact)
 - Increased research income
 - New commercial revenue
 - Access to new markets /customers or investors
 - Increased publications
 - Engagement in new research field
 - Strategic repositioning
 - (New) strategy for commercial exploitation
 - Enhanced knowledge base /improved internal skills
 - Enhanced career prospects
 - Enhanced reputation /network visibility
 - Environmental or social improvements
 - Better evidence for decisions
 - New international collaboration opportunities
 - Durable collaboration with international peers
- Other, please specify
- How do the impacts achieved to date compare with those that were anticipated at the beginning of the project? (from (1) much lower to (5) much higher)

YOUR ORGANISATIONAL LEARNING

- As a result of participation in this M-ERA.Net funded project, has your organisation (yes, partially, no):
 - Entered new partnerships
 - Changed its R&D strategy
 - Developed sustainability /Responsible Research &Innovation (RRI)strategy
 - Engaged more with end-users
 - Participated in other EU /international calls
 - Changed view on transnational collaboration
 - If possible, please provide examples for the above
 - Further comments
 -

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION (RRI)

- To what extent did your project(s) address the following: (from (1) not addressed to (5) fully addressed):
 - Societal relevance
 - Environmental relevance
 - Ethics

- Gender equality
- Open science /data protection
- Stakeholder engagement
- To what extent are the RRI guidelines provided by M-ERA.NET helpful in addressing these aspects? (from (1) not helpful to (5) very helpful)
- Further comments?

FEEDBACK ON NETWORK MANAGEMENT

- How would you rate the following in relation to the management of the M-ERA.NET programme? (from (1) very poor to (5) excellent):
 - Quality of call topic definition
 - Ease of proposal submission -Guidance from your national/regional funding agency
 - Transparency of evaluation
 - Usefulness of the evaluation feedback on your proposal
 - Clarity of M-ERA.NET funding rules at national/regional level
 - Sufficiency of financial resources
 - Overall call timeline – from application to decision for funding
 - Coordination across funders
 - Communication from project coordinator
 - Quality of collaboration within the project consortium
 - Monitoring and reporting requirements
 - Further comments?

ANTICIPATED WIDER IMPACTS

- What wider impacts have you achieved to date, or do you anticipate achieving following completion of the project(s)? (low, moderate, high, no impact):
 - Creation of new jobs
 - Contribution to environmental sustainability
 - Improvements in public health/ safety / well-being
 - Input to policy /regulation
 - Educational use (tools / training)
 - Advancement of related scientific /technical fields
 - Advancement in the field of advanced materials
 - Other, please specify
 - Further comments?

PROPOSAL PROCESS

- How would you rate the clarity of the call documents and guidelines? (from (1) very unclear to (10) very clear)
- Did you receive sufficient guidance and support from: (from (1) not helpful at all to (5) very helpful)
 - National contact point

- M-ERA.NET
 - coordinators
 - Other partners in your consortium
- Did you receive feedback on your proposal?
 - Yes, detailed and useful
 - Yes, but limited in detail
 - No feedback received
- If your project was not funded, what was the main barrier?
 - Scientific / technical weaknesses identified by evaluators
 - Insufficient budget allocated to the project
 - Consortium weaknesses (partners, balance, geography)
 - Misalignment with call topics
 - Inability to secure national funding
 - Other
- Did you feel the evaluation process was fair? (yes, partially, no)
- Despite being unsuccessful, did participation in the application process bring any benefits?
 - New collaborations
 - Insights into future R&D priorities
 - Improved understanding of the application process
 - No benefit
 - Other
- What did you do with your project idea that was not selected for funding under M-ERA.NET?
 - Applied in another programme but the decision is still pending
 - No decision has been taken yet on what to do with this project idea
 - We abandoned the specific project idea
 - Got funded under a national programme call
 - Got funding under another international programme
 - Other
- If funded under another international programme, please specify
- If you got funding in another programme, how does the accepted project compare to the one that you applied for under M-ERA.NET? (lower, similar, higher)
 - Ambition and objectives
 - International collaboration
 - Number of partners
 - Total budget
 - Scientific /technological scope
 - Inter-disciplinarity
- What improvements would you suggest for future M-ERA.NET calls to make participation easier and more effective?

FINAL REFLECTIONS

- From your experience of participating in M-ERA.NET funded projects, what do you consider to be:
 - The main success factors
 - The main barriers or challenges faced
 - Do you have any further feedback or suggestions?
- Do you consent to being contacted for follow-up questions or to support the creation of a case study?

APPENDIX B: INTERVIEW TEMPLATE FOR M-ERA.NET MEMBERS AND EC OFFICIALS

Interviewee

Name:

Organisation:

M-ERA.NET 3 Affiliation:

Position in M-ERA.NET 3:

Interviewer

Name:

Organisation:

Interview

Date:

A. Motivations and extent of participation

1. What are your country's our region's primary motivations and commitment level regarding M-ERA.NET 3? Have these changed over time? (even since M-ERA.NET 2 or 1)
 2. What specific national/regional/organizational factors (policies, capacity, flexibility in aligning rules, timing, etc.) influence your performance in M-ERA.NET 3, including both challenges and advantages? (policy level, institutional level, capacity level, instrument level, other?)
 3. Do you believe your national/regional commitment aligns with your research community's interest and is adequate for fostering critical mass in advanced materials at the EU level?
-

B. Network performance

1. What were the initial expectations for your participation in M-ERA.NET 3, and to what extent have they been met? Why or why not? (mobilisation of critical mass, alignment and coordination of national/regional programmes, enhanced trans-national cooperation, long-term cooperation and durability, contribution to EGD, technological leadership, etc.)
2. What are the key good practices and obstacles/ difficulties encountered in M-ERA.NET 3's design, operation, and management? What has worked well and what needs to be improved? (In relation to governance, efficiency of resources needed vis a vis the outcome gained, call definition and implementation, time-to-grant, attracting the R&I community and industry, distribution of the EU top-up funding, additional activities, monitoring and evaluation, dissemination/up-take of results, etc.)
3. Are there any areas in which you believe that M-ERA.NET 3 is underperforming and, if so, what are they and why (e.g. policy influence, economic impact, social impact, alignment, other)?

C. Network health, connectivity, and operation

1. Is the network overly dependent on a few individuals/organizations? Does the current membership possess the necessary capacities (experience, skills, connections, resources), and are there any critical missing connections (with countries, organisations or specific stakeholder groups)? Is membership adjusted to meet changing network needs and policy contexts?

2. How has your organisation internally managed M-ERA.NET 3 participation? Have you created new roles, structures, or processes in response to the demands of the network?
3. Is the network's governance flexible enough to adapt to changing needs (changing policy contexts, EU/ national priorities, industry needs, etc.) and do all members share a common vision and trust?
4. How effective is the call topic definition process, ensuring complementarity and addressing changing policy priorities and cutting-edge emerging tech and application areas?
5. How has Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) been interpreted, developed, and integrated into M-ERA.NET 3, including its usefulness and challenges?
6. How valuable or effective is peer to peer learning and informal exchange within the network?

D. Impacts

1. What positive and negative impacts have your country/region/organization experienced from M-ERA.NET 3 participation or has M-ERA.NET 3 created as a network? (**positive**: e.g. long-term connectivity, capacity building and improved processes within funding agencies, conceptual/ policy impact influencing national or European policies, e.g. the new Advanced Materials for Industrial Leadership communication, structural impacts as in creation of national coordination structures, economic like more investments at national level in the area, and systemic impacts like alignment/ convergence of programmes, etc., **negative**: e.g. resource intensity, reduced funds at national level or other transnational initiatives, rate of return not as expected, other?) Have there been any unforeseen impacts?
2. Have your funded projects shown early signs of success (e.g., spin-offs, patents, industrial uptake) or are there any success stories from monitored projects that could be examined in more detail?

E. Strategic positioning

1. How has the broader policy context changed since M-ERA.NET 3's launch (e.g. from societal challenges and SDGs to competitiveness and European leadership and tech sovereignty, from NMBP to Cluster 4, other?), and how has this impacted its position at the EU level? (vis a vis other framework programs, Cluster 4 calls, other networks/ partnerships, the new co-programmed partnership, etc.)
2. What is the position of M-ERA.NET 3 in your national/ regional R&I portfolio/ strategy? Has it changed over time? (central instrument with M-ERA.NET funded projects contributing to national roadmaps or policy development in advanced materials, for example, rather put aside, just an additional funding source, other?)
3. Describe any synergies achieved with other networks/ partnerships/ initiatives and the measures taken to ensure complementarity and multiply impact.

F. Comparison of M-ERA.NET 3 with other similar networks/ partnerships

1. Compared to similar networks, how do coordination costs and committed funds vis a vis attracted applications and funded projects differ for M-ERA.NET 3? (provide examples and data if available)
2. What other relevant comparisons can be made across these networks? Are there any examples of good practice that M-ERA.NET could adopt or adapt?

G. Future outlook

1. What is your ambition for the partnership in the next framework programme, and what role do you envision for your organization?
2. Is the proposed M-ERA.NET 4 format suitable to fully leverage the level of alignment and transnational collaboration achieved thus far?

General

1. Are there any additional points you wish to make that we have not addressed?
2. Can you identify different patterns of participation (e.g., selective, broad funding, "free riding") among M-ERA.NET 3 countries/agencies? (Some countries are more selective than others, some may be showing a 'free riding' attitude, others may be participating in almost anything with strong funds, others spread their national funds thinly)

Many thanks for your feedback and collaboration!

A short summary of the main conclusions of our discussion will be sent to you immediately for comments/approval.

We'd also appreciate your approval about the following:

- Names will not be disclosed due to GDPR rules but your organisation, will be include in the acknowledgement section of the report – YES/NO
- Certain quotes may be used in the main body of the report that will be attributed to 'Organisation X officials' – YES/NO

APPENDIX C: INTERVIEW TEMPLATE FOR FUNDED R&I PROJECT COORDINATORS

Interviewee

Name:

Organisation:

Role in M-ERA.NET 3 Project:

Interviewer

Name:

Organisation:

Interview

Date:

A. Project Overview and Background

1. How did your consortium come together (was it built through existing networks/ contacts or new collaborations)? Regarding the project consortium, was the transnational setup beneficial or challenging?
2. Was your research approach interdisciplinary? If so, was this in terms of scientific and technological fields and / or the types of stakeholders involved? What was the impact of this approach?
3. Did the overall project budget include any in-kind contribution from industry?

B. Proposal Process and Support

1. How did you find the call documentation and guidance during the application phase?
2. Was the application process clear, transparent, and manageable?
3. Did you receive any support from national/regional funding bodies or the M-ERA.NET call secretariat during the submission or contracting stages?

C. Project Implementation and Collaboration

1. Have you faced any major delays, challenges or changes (communication, decision-making, task division, lack of specific expertise)? Did your project receive the full funding requested (if not, why and how did this impact your implementation)?
2. How do you assess the RRI requirements in the proposal and project implementation? How have they affected, if at all, the organisation and implementation of the research activities and the dissemination of the results?
3. What types of infrastructure* (i.e. transnational/national public/private, technological/institutional etc.) has the project used in the activities? Has the project accessed infrastructure available within the consortium? Has it established links with facilities/ structures of organisations outside?

(Infrastructures are capital-intensive / high cost investments that are essential for R&I. These may be physical artefacts such as technological platforms, networks and communication networks. They can be high-cost machines such as testing facilities and machinery or non-physical assets such as databases and other data repositories.)

D. Output, Outcomes and Impacts

1. Have there been any (early) outputs or outcomes or signs of impacts you would highlight (publications, patents, prototypes, new areas, new/changes in strategies, careers, new / strengthened collaborations, policy influence, promising technological advancement, education and training, other)? Of those, which would you rate as the top three outcomes/ impacts of your project? (Please provide data if any available that support your statements)
2. In terms of TRL, what was the starting TRL and is the expected/resultant TRL – were there any additional outputs, outcomes or impacts that you didn't expect?
3. How strategic has this project been for your organisation? Is it part of a wider project portfolio leading to the achievement of your business goals?
4. What plans do you have or steps that you have taken to exploit the results (have you used experts services to assist you, such as technology transfer organisations and consultancy services and are you engaging with, for example, providers of funding)? How have you accessed specialised knowledge (regulatory, technical, other?) that is not available in-house? Is there any kind of support mechanism or tool M-ERA.NET could provide to enable the exploitation / upscaling / uptake of the results of your project?
5. Have you identified and engaged with potential end users? Is there any specific pathway that you need to follow to move further down the line of innovation generation?
6. What are the most important (critical) factors to move forward towards exploitation of results? How can these be ensured within a project under M-ERA.NET? What other programmes or initiatives need to be linked to achieve progress in exploitation?
7. Do you expect the collaboration to continue beyond the project (if so, in what form)? Are there any plans for a follow up project? (if so in which programme)? Are these plans a result of your involvement in M-ERA.NET.
8. Was/is the project continuing previous R&I efforts in the same field or is it opening a new field for you or your organisation?
9. Overall, what would you say are the positive impacts and the negative experiences on your organisation from your participation in the M-ERA.NET project(s)?
10. Is there any other aspect in relation to the exploitation of the project's results that we have not taken into consideration in this interview, and you wish to point out?

E. Added Value

11. What added value has M-ERA.NET 3 brought to your project compared to national funding (e.g., scientific excellence, international access, technology readiness, industrial uptake, other)?

12. What added value has M-ERA.NET 3 brought to your project compared to other EU funding like the Horizon Europe programme, or partnerships like ERA-MIN, etc. (e.g., scientific excellence, international access, technology readiness, industrial uptake, other)?
13. To what extent has the project contributed to EU or global objectives or policy development (e.g., Green Deal, SDGs, digital/green transitions)?

F. Feedback and Recommendations

1. Were there any elements that could be improved in future calls / M-ERA.NET 4? (application process, communication, reporting, monitoring and evaluation, supporting exploitation of results, etc.)
2. Would you participate in a similar programme again? (why or why not)
3. Is there anything else you'd like to share that might help improve the programme or assess its impact?

Many thanks for your feedback and collaboration!

A short summary of the main conclusions of our discussion will be sent to you immediately for comments/approval.

We'd also appreciate your approval about the following:

Names will not be disclosed due to GDPR rules but your organisation, will be include in the acknowledgement section of the report – YES/NO

Certain quotes may be used in the main body of the report that will be attributed to 'M-ERA.NET 3 beneficiary' – YES/NO

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